

**DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF EMOAI SMART CLASSROOM: A STUDENT
EMOTIONAL AND BEHAVIORAL ENGAGEMENT RECOGNITION SYSTEM**

ABDULSALAM FOLASEWA MARYAM

CSC/2016/001

**A FINAL YEAR PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER
SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING, FACULTY OF TECHNOLOGY,
OBAFEMI AWOLOWO UNIVERSITY, ILE-IFE.**

**IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF
BACHELOR OF SCIENCE (B.Sc.) DEGREE IN COMPUTER SCIENCE WITH
MATHEMATICS**

AUGUST, 2023

CERTIFICATION

The undersigned certify that they have read, approved, and hereby recommend to the Faculty of Technology, a research project titled “Design and Implementation of EmoAI Smart Classroom: A Student Emotional and Behavioral Engagement Recognition System” originally written by Folasewa Maryam Abdulsalam in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of a Bachelor of Science Degree (B. Sc) in Computer Science with Mathematics.

Dr. A.O Afolabi

(Project Supervisor)

Prof. A.O Oluwatope

(Head of Department)

Date

Date

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to you, Folasewa, your parents and siblings; and most importantly to your creator.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Grateful to the Almighty for bringing me thus far; throughout my studentship, I had zero visits to the hospital, no cause to miss lectures or exams. My profound gratitude goes to my supervisor Dr. Afolabi. I would not have asked for a better supervisor. The push needed for me to see this to the end came from you, thank you!

My gratitude will be incomplete without mentioning my parents and siblings; Mr. and Mrs. Salami, Bolarinwa Salami, and Zainab Salami. You all gave me the reason to see this to the end.

To my reading partners, Jane, Precious, Ope, Promise; to my codes debugger, Bolu; to David who gave me his laptop to work; and Oluwaseun for the support; I say thank you very much for contributing to the success of this project. See you all at the top.

TABLE OF CONTENT

Title Page	
Certification.....	i
Dedication	ii
Acknowledgment.....	iii
Table of Content.....	iv
List of Tables	ix
List of Figures.....	x
Abstract	xii

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study.....	1
1.2 Statement of Problem.....	6
1.3 Scope and limitation of Project	6
1.4 Justification.....	7
1.5 Aim and Objectives.....	7
1.6 Methodology	8
1.7 Expected Contribution to Knowledge.....	8
1.8 Application to Educational Support	8
1.9 Organization of Report.....	9

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1	Introduction.....	10
2.2	Conceptual Review.....	10
2.2.1	Smart Classroom.....	11
2.2.2	Learning Analytics in a Smart Classroom.....	12
2.3	Affective Computing.....	14
2.4	Deep Learning	14
2.4.1	Deep Learning neural networks.....	15
2.4.2	Deep Learning use cases.....	16.
2.4.3	Deep Learning Challenges.....	16
2.5	Computer Vision.....	18
2.5.1	Uses of Computer Vision in Education	18
2.5.2	Computer Vision in Education and Privacy.....	19
2.6	Facial Emotion Recognition System.....	20
2.6.1	Face Recognition.....	20
2.6.2	Head Pose Estimation.....	21
2.6.3	Eye Gaze Measurement.....	22
2.6.4	Hand-Over-Face Gestures in Learning and Teaching.....	23

2.7 Student Engagement Systems	24
2.7.1 Engagement Estimation Methods	25
2.7.1.1 Manual Method	26.
2.7.1.2 Semi-Automatic Methods	26
2.7.1.3 Automatic Methods	27
2.8 Related Works	28

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction	38
3.1 Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC)	38
3.1.1 Requirement Gathering and Analysis Phase	40
3.1.2 System Design	41
3.1.2.1 Unified Modeling Language (UML)	42
3.1.2.2 System Framework	42.
3.1.2.3 Use Case Diagram	48
3.1.2.4 Activity Diagram	48
3.1.2.5 Class Diagram	52
3.1.2.6 Sequence Diagram	55

CHAPTER FOUR: SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION AND EVALUATION

4.1	Introduction.....	57
4.2	Implementation at Model Level.....	57
4.2.1	The DAiSEE Dataset.....	58
4.2.2	Data Collection.....	58
4.2.3	Frame Extraction.....	59
4.2.4	Data Annotation.....	59
4.2.5	Model Building.....	60
4.3	Tools Used.....	64
4.4	Implementation at Design Level.....	66
4.4.1	Functional Requirements.....	66
4.4.2	User Interface Prototype.....	66
4.5	Workflow of the Integration of the Model and User Interface.....	73
4.6	Tools Used.....	77
4.7	Evaluation.....	78
4.7.1	Alpha Testing.....	78.
4.7.2	Objectives of Alpha Testing.....	78
4.7.3	Parameters used in Evaluation.....	79

CHAPTER FIVE: SUMMARY, CHALLENGES, AND CONCLUSION

5.1	Introduction.....	81
------------	--------------------------	-----------

5.2 Conclusion.....	81.
5.3 Challenges Encountered.....	82
5.4 Recommendations.....	82
REFERENCES.....	83
APPENDIX A	92

LIST OF TABLES

Table 2.1 Literature Review Table.....	34
Table 4.1 Result of the Evaluation.....	79

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2.1 – Deep Learning as a subset of AI.....	17
Figure 2.2 – Uses of Computer Vision Analysis in Education.....	20
Figure 2.3 – Areas of application of HPE.....	22
Figure 2.4- HPE Framework.....	22
Figure 2.5- Common Hand-over-face gestures.....	24
Figure 2.6 – Taxonomy of Learner’s engagement detection methods.....	28
Figure 3.1-SDLC Framework.....	39
Figure 3.2—Proposed Framework by Pabba and Kumar (2021).....	45
Figure 3.3—System Framework.....	45
Figure 3.4 Proposed Framework flowchart (Pabba and Kumar, 2021).....	46
Figure 3.5 System Flowchart.....	47
Figure 3.6—Use case diagram for EmoAI Smart Classroom.....	50
Figure 3.7 Activity Diagram for EmoAI Smart Classroom.....	51
Figure 3.8—Class Diagram of EmoAI Smart Classroom.....	54
Figure 3.9—Sequence Diagram of EmoAI Smart Classroom.....	56
Figure 4.1 Implementation at Model Level.....	57
Figure 4.2 Annotation on RoboFlow.....	60
Figure 4.3 Result of the pre-processing steps.....	61

Figure 4.4 Class loss results.....	63
Figure 4.5 Screenshot of an uploaded classroom video.....	64
Figure 4.6 Implementation at Design Level.....	66
Figure 4.7 Splash Screen.....	67
Figure 4.8 Student Sign Up Page.....	67
Figure 4.9 Student Log-in Page.....	68
Figure 4.10 Lecturer Sign Up Page.....	69
Figure 4.11 Lecturer Log in Page.....	70
Figure 4.12 Video Upload.....	71
Figure 4.13 Engagement Analysis.....	72
Figure 4.14 Interface of the Strapi Dashboard.....	75
Figure 4.15 A new user (admin) is created.....	76
Figure 4.16 The Engagement report dashboard.....	76

ABSTRACT

The issue of student disengagement has become critical in the current educational system as a result of numerous distractions and lack of interactions between students and teachers. This issue gets worse in large offline classes because it emotionally tasking for teachers to monitor student engagement and maintain the right level of interaction simultaneously. By understanding the fundamental academic affective states displayed by students in the classroom, the dynamics of a lecture can be better understood and improved.

Hence, an emotional and behavioral engagement system that detects and analyzes academic affective states and behaviors of students in the classroom while sending a feedback to the lecturer was proposed in this project.

The Dataset used is DAiSEE (Dataset for Affective States in E-Environment), the architecture used is YOLO V8, Unified Modelling Language (UML) was used to design the system, Python was used to implement using RoboFlow Framework, and the system was evaluated through testing of pre-recorded classroom videos.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Human behavior can be expressed in part through communication. Humans communicate their emotions both verbally and nonverbally. Through our facial expressions, bodily movements, posture, eye contact, hand gestures, tone and volume of voice, and micro expressions, we employ nonverbal cues to speak to others. An essential component of non-verbal communication is facial expression (*Jayashree et al., 2014*). However, interpreting messages from body positions is a crucial part of how we communicate (*Kret et al., 2013*).

As the "organ of emotion," the face is continuously being read by us to ascertain how others are feeling. It is perhaps the most effective non-verbal "channel." As a result, behavioral scientists have been actively researching the study of face movement since Darwin's work in 1872. (*Akkabany, et al., 2019*).

Although physical expressions are also playing a bigger role in emotion expression, traditional emotion theories still place a lot of emphasis on the face. In affective neuroscience, which has until now been primarily concerned with studies of face expressions, the perception of physical expressions is a relatively new issue. However, bodies and faces frequently communicate the same information about identity, emotion, and gender in daily life and are both prominent and familiar.

A person's discrete emotional state, such as happiness, rage, or boredom, can be inferred from the configurations of various micro motor (small muscle) movements in the face (*Harley,2015*). For

starters, facial expressions are the most traditional and continue to be among the finest indicators of emotional states due to their extensive use and unrivaled level of accuracy compared to most other, more recently established techniques (*Calvo & D'Mello, 2010; Zeng et al., 2009*). Body language also reveals a person's propensity for action in addition to facial expressions. Body postures and facial expressions are perceived in an interactive and context-dependent manner (*Kret and de Gelder, 2012a*). As a means of communication between people and computers, body language is becoming increasingly significant. The tracking and classification of affective body movement and body posture can be used to track, classify, and describe bodily expressions in addition to facial expressions.

Since emotions are sometimes transitory, obscured, and conflicted, measuring them can be challenging. Understanding a student's emotional state is crucial for a teacher to have even though it might be challenging to measure emotions (*Tullis, et al 2013*). Emotions and learning are closely intertwined, and they play a significant role in creating the learning environment (*Shuck et al., 2007*). Interaction between emotions and cognition influences rational conduct, such as memory and decision-making (*Woolf et al., 2010*). Effective learning and teaching depend more and more on understanding and modeling students' emotions and behaviors. In order to determine a student's emotional state in a classroom setting, most teachers employ a combination of probing questions, interpretation of their facial expressions, and even body language.

The basic-emotion approach, a particular scientific framework, postulates that instances of a certain emotion category are expressed with facial movements that fluctuate, to some extent, around a typical set of movements, known as a prototype. For instance, it is proposed that in a specific circumstance or for a specific person, rage may be represented by the facial prototype (such as furrowed brows, enlarged eyes, and pursed lips) as well as other facial gestures (*Barrett*

et al., 2019). The basic-emotion approach, however, continues to operate under the presumption that there exists a basic facial configuration that serves as the prototype and can be used to identify an individual's emotional state in a manner similar to how a fingerprint can be used to uniquely identify a person. This hereby supports the argument that one of the clues for determining a person's emotional state is their facial expression.

Numerous research fields, including computer science (*Michel and Kaliouby, 2005*), neuroscience (*Liu et al., 2012*), psychology (*Ekman and Oster, 1979*), and medicine, have extensively studied emotion recognition in both theory and applications. It is a crucial step in the process of a machine understanding human behavior.

The capacity to identify and analyze another person's feelings is known as emotion recognition. It is a technique that examines emotions in various media, including images and videos. It is a member of the group of technologies known as "affective computing," a multidisciplinary area of study on how well computers can understand and detect affective states and human emotions. Affective computing frequently builds on Artificial Intelligence technology.

Since a few years ago, there has been a sharp increase in interest in creating technology that can identify people's affective states (*Fragopanagos & Taylor, 2005*), with the idea of deducing affect from body language receiving particular attention. The numerous non-digital applications for security, law enforcement, gaming and entertainment, education, health care, and security show the relevance of body expressions and the advantages of creating apps into which influence detection from body expressions may be integrated. The application field of interest is the education sector in monitoring students' attention and detecting engagement in a learning environment using facial and body cues.

The stress of labor-intensive classroom tasks like attendance tracking, gathering lecture feedback, student involvement, or attention monitoring is decreased with the introduction of intelligent technologies in big offline classroom management, reinforcing the best teaching-learning outcomes (*Kim et al., 2018*).

The quality of the overall classroom learning experience and academic success are improved when students are actively participating in the learning process (*De Villiers & Werner, 2016*). The issue of student disengagement is currently getting worse every day due to a variety of factors, including poor teaching methods, a limited attention span, and a lack of student-teacher interactions (*Bradbury, 2016*). The presence of big offline classrooms (student count is greater or equal to 60) exacerbates this issue

In order to improve the educational system, student engagement—which occurs when a student participates meaningfully in the learning environment—should be carefully considered (*Sharma et al., 2019*). According to the definition of student engagement by (*Lamborn et al., 2014*), it is the psychological commitment a student makes to learning and comprehending the concepts or abilities that their academic work aims to promote. Achievement of students is directly correlated with engagement (*Furrer et al., 2014*).

Students' participation is described using multiple aspects and components in the literature on educational research. It was characterized by (*Fredricks et al. 2004*) in terms of behavioral, emotional, and cognitive engagements. Behaviors like maintaining good posture and taking notes are examples of behaviors that are described as being engaged in the learning process. Positive and negative emotional responses to learning, such as focus, boredom, and irritation, are referred to as emotional involvement. Learning to improve cognitive abilities, such as knowledge, problem-solving, and creative thinking, comes via cognitive engagement. It is possible to identify a student's

level of involvement during a lecture since behavioral and emotional engagements are inversely correlated (*Li & Lerner 2013*) and behavioral engagement influences cognitive engagement, a crucial result of the learning process.

Students' feelings during class participation are crucial in any learning environment (*Krithika et al., 2016*). Emotions can have an impact on how pupils learn (*Turner et al., 2002*). It may have an impact on a student's concentration, drive to learn, coping mechanisms, and self-control (*Skinner, et al., 2014*). It may also provide crucial cues regarding how well they are studying in class.

There is some evidence that some emotions, such as boredom (*Csikszentmihalyi, 1990*), perplexity (*Graesser & Olde, 2003; Klein, & Picard, 2002*), flow (also known as engagement, *Csikszentmihalyi, 1990*), and frustration, might affect learning and cognition (*Klein, & Picard, 2002*). Also thought to go along with learning are curiosity and eureka moments, or "a-ha" moments.

The dynamics of a lecture can be better understood and improved upon by knowing and enhancing the students' attention span, which is a fundamental emotion shown in the classroom by the students. In-class attention spans among students range from 46% to 67%, according to studies (*Raca et al., 2015*). As a result, it can be assumed that up to 50% of the students are not capable of learning effectively. Determining the possible causes of this scenario as well as the circumstances in which some pupils lose focus more frequently than others is vital. With this knowledge in hand, teachers can look for potential issues during lessons and strive to fix them, which could improve the students' learning effectiveness (*Canedo & Neves, 2020*). Different emotions are evoked in a classroom setting, which might influence whether learning occurs or not. One of the special affective states that cannot be characterized by the fundamental emotions is the academic affective state (*Wei et al., 2017*).

With the tremendous advancement in computer vision techniques, significant academic affective states that are relevant to a learning environment (*Tonguc & Ozkara, 2020*) will be reviewed and implemented in this study using a non-invasive approach to measure in real time student emotional and behavioral engagement in the classroom. These states include "boredom," "confusion," "focus," "frustration," and "sleepy."

1.2 Statement of Problem

The issue of student disengagement has become critical in the current educational system as a result of numerous distractions and lack of interactions between the students and the teachers. The frequent overcrowding in offline classrooms makes it emotionally draining for teachers to monitor students' moods thoroughly, maintain the correct degree of interaction and obtain rapid learning feedback from all students while learning is occurring (*Chen, et al.,2019*).

To better understand and improve the dynamics of lectures delivered, it is necessary to develop an engagement system that takes into account both academic-affective states and the body language displayed by students in relation to engagement or disengagement.

1.3 Scope and limitation of the Project

The system developed is context-specific for inferring affect through visible unintended gestures made by students in tutoring situations. It is limited to detecting hand-over-gestures and four academic affective states.

Case study is OGD Tutors, a tutorial center situated at OAU Central market, Ile-Ife, Osun State.

The video and image data needed for evaluation were collected from the students.

1.4 Justification

This study explores the relationship between student emotions and body language and engagement and attention span, as well as if these cues can help lecturers enhance the dynamics of the lecture

in the classroom. The real-time student behavioral and emotional engagement recognition system required for effective learning in large classrooms is one that can provide a thorough analysis of the students' emotions while a lecture is going on without bias and without putting an emotional strain on the instructor giving the lecture.

The development of this system will become an important tool for educators and schools. Teachers will be able to identify students who may be struggling with learning in the classroom, and adjust their teaching methods accordingly; schools will make informed decisions about the curriculum, teacher training and student support services.

This ultimately provides a system with an improved quality of education for students, promote academic success, and support the development of well-rounded individuals.

1.5 Aim and Objectives

The aim of this thesis is to develop a student emotional and behavioral engagement recognition system. The Specific objectives are to:

- i. collect video data
- ii. identify student emotions and behaviors
- iii. understand engagement levels of the students and
- iv. evaluate the system

1.6 Methodology

- i. Video data (DAiSEE) was collected from Paper with Code
- ii. Frames were extracted from the data and annotated using LabelAssist on RoboFlow
- iii. The extracted frames were trained on YOLO V8 pre-trained model
- iv. The model was evaluated through testing of pre-recorded classroom videos.

1.7 Expected Contribution to Knowledge

This study will contribute to the existing body of knowledge by

- i. providing a system that caters for both body gestures and emotions related to learning in the classroom;
- ii. providing a system in which tutors can evaluate their teaching methodologies through the result of engagement analysis.

1.8 Application to Educational Support

It is challenging to observe all students' mental states in time to determine their level of learning for both offline and online instruction. We conducted a thorough investigation of automatic intelligent monitoring technologies in the classroom to help tutors and lecturers better understand the learning level of each student. We recommend that such technologies be put into place in combination with human teachers since they will help them mentally connect with the students' learning status and provide insight into the positive and negative emotions displayed throughout a lecture. This would enable educators to focus more of their attention on pupils who consistently display unfavorable learning emotions, which would improve the quality of the learning materials. The dynamics of the lectures will be much improved, the teacher's workload will be lessened because he has a system serving as his third eye to connect with the students on a similar mental level, and lectures will be presented better taking into account the emotions of the students.

1.9 Organization of Report

This project is sectioned into five (5) chapters. Chapter one gives the background of the project, its scope, and objectives. It also states the problems of the study, methodology, and justification. Chapter two presents a review of existing literature on student classroom engagement systems and facial emotion detection systems.

Chapter three elaborates the steps, procedures, and methodologies employed in the design, development, and implementation of student classroom engagement systems and facial emotion detection systems. It gives comprehensive information about the tools used to implement the project.

Chapter four, discusses the UI design and the implementation of the project which include the logical and physical design; the system is also evaluated for efficiency. The efficiency is determined by how much the system is able to meet the requirements.

The flaws noticed are documented so that they can be modified and updated for the improvement of the future version of the system.

Chapter five is the concluding chapter which contains the limitations and challenges encountered, a summary of the work done, and recommendations to be used for future project analysis and conclusion.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

Literature review discusses the research and analysis of existing systems and the implementation of possible techniques and methods to use in the project. This is done to determine the best possible techniques and methods so that the feasibility of the project can be determined. In this project, related topics are: smart classroom, emotion recognition, hand-over-face recognition system, real time systems, facial recognition, body pose estimation, student engagement system implementation in the education field. Since these topics are closely related to the project, the researcher is expected to make references in implementation of a real time student emotional and behavioral engagement system.

2.2 Conceptual Review

A person's ability to learn cognitive procedures have been encouraged and accepted by many researchers. Some research also found the need to develop learning systems that can detect the emotional states of learners; hence finding indexes to determine the engagement and concentration levels based on their emotional states has been gaining ground in recent years.

Robotic tutors, e-learning, and Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITSs), which would offer individualized education across a variety of subjects, have recently attracted a lot of attention (*Gordon et al., 2016; Andallaza et al., 2012; Woolf, 2010; D'Mello et al., 2005*). These systems typically infer affective states merely from facial expressions and can personalize to some level, but they lack the requisite empathic skills, that is, the capacity to fully understand learners' emotions, moods, and temperaments. The following sub-section will give a comprehensive

overview of areas related to creating a smart classroom using an automatic student emotional and behavioral system.

2.2.1 Smart Classroom

The study and development of novel technologies and sciences for replicating, extending, and enhancing human intelligence is known as artificial intelligence (*Zhang and Chen, 2021*).

Artificial intelligence technology has advanced quickly along with the growth of mobile information, altering every aspect of our lives. It is possible to construct intelligent and efficient classroom instruction and improve students' ideological development by deeply integrating and innovating artificial intelligence technology into classroom education and teaching.

The term 'smart classroom' means an intelligent classroom based on artificial intelligence technologies by integrating in an unobtrusive manner the different components in a traditional classroom to improve learning process. In this regard, smart classrooms play a significant role in the transformation of conventional education into modern education (*Hicham, and Abdelaziz, 2017*), which presents prospects for enhancing educational quality and academic ability, access to quality education, and fairness.

The various parts of a smart classroom produce a lot of activity-related data, which provides the opportunity to extract insightful knowledge that might be applied to enhance the learning process and help the component parts' educational decision-making (*Aguilar, et al, 2017*).

However, in a smart classroom, it is extremely difficult to share and manipulate this kind of information in real time. This is the area where learning analytics activities in a smart classroom are applied to improve its behavior.

2.2.2 Learning Analytics in a Smart Classroom

Understanding and identifying the various learning capacities of the students is crucial in a smart classroom so that teachers may provide the students the direction they need to advance their skills. Sharing and modifying insightful knowledge created in the classroom in real time is the area of application of learning analytics activities in a smart classroom (*Aguilar et al., 2017*). In a smart classroom, Learning Analytics often aims to achieve two distinct objectives (*Valdiviezo et al., 2015*)

1. To comprehend the student learning: Learning Analytics will need to produce indicators about it (framework, methodologies, tools, etc.);
2. To comprehend the behavior of the students: in this scenario, the learning analytics tasks must produce metrics indicating the effectiveness of each student.

For the proposed EmoAI smart classroom, we propose a set of Learning Analytics tasks such as:

1. Recognition of the students in the smart classroom: this task involves face recognition of the students by matching up each student's face with their name in a database.
2. Monitoring the learning process of students in the smart classroom: this task involves the identification of lecture periods at which the maximum and minimum learning took place through their behavioral engagement in the classroom

Some of the technologies to be employed include facial recognition systems that use cameras to capture student responses, algorithms to identify their attention levels, and measuring smiles, frowns and audio to classify student engagement, “each using a combination of psychology and data-mining to detect micro expressions and classify human reactions.”

2.3 Affective Computing

We must give computers the ability to perceive, understand, and even have and express emotions if we want them to be truly intelligent and communicate naturally with us. - *Rosalind W. Picard 1997.*

The subject area of affective computing focuses on the creation of tools and processes that can identify, understand, and elaborate on human emotions. In this multidisciplinary discipline, computer science, psychology, and cognitive science are all represented.

Given that shifting emotional states of students can have a significant impact on their ability to learn, affective computing is currently believed to be crucial in the field of online learning. It recognizes the user's emotional state and reacts suitably. By using the power of emotion, this research area aims to enhance human-human communication and human-computer interaction. The fact that affective computing has made it possible for or will make it possible for users to interact with computers more effectively, compassionately, and amiably excites scientists, researchers, and system engineers.

Over the past ten years, researchers have examined a variety of aspects of affective computing in education and learning, including the role of the teacher in managing students' emotions, the impact of gender, and the relationship between shape and color and emotion and learning (*Lavy & Eshet, 2018*).

However, more in-depth research is necessary to make these understandings applicable to real-world situations because emotional computing research studies, particularly in the educational domain, are substantially larger and less developed than in other domains (*Huang, & Hwang, 2015*). The educational technology blog EdSurge has published a piece on "emotive computing"

in the classroom. According to the article, teaching computer-based robots to "understand emotional states based on signals and then react accordingly depending on an estimate of how the person is feeling" is what is meant by "emotional computing." Robots may be more useful in this role than humans since they are not affected by emotion and instead use sophisticated technology to unearth hidden responses.

2.4 Deep Learning

A subset of machine learning called "Deep Learning" (*Fig. 2.1*) is inspired by information-processing patterns discovered in the human brain. Deep Learning does not require any rules created by humans in order to work; instead, it uses a vast amount of data to map input to predetermined labels. Artificial neural networks, or ANNs, are used in Deep Learning to create numerous layers of algorithms, each of which provides a distinct interpretation of the input data (*Zhang et al., 2020*). Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning techniques known as deep learning are akin to how people learn particular sorts of information. Deep learning can be thought of as the most fundamental form of automation for predictive analytics. As opposed to the linear algorithms used in most machine learning applications, these algorithms are stacked in a hierarchy of increasing complexity and abstraction. Deep learning has the advantage that the feature set is built by the software independently.

To attain an acceptable level of accuracy, deep learning systems need vast amounts of training data and processing power, neither of which were previously commonly available to programmers before to the big data and cloud computing era.

2.4.1 Deep Learning neural networks

A type of sophisticated machine learning approach called an artificial neural network underpins the majority of deep learning models. Deep learning is also referred to as deep neural learning or deep neural networking as a result.

There are many different kinds of neural networks, each with advantages for particular use cases, such as recurrent neural networks, convolutional neural networks, artificial neural networks, and feedforward neural networks. However, they all function essentially in the same ways: they provide data to the model and let it decide whether or not it has correctly interpreted or judged a particular data element. Neural networks need a lot of data to train on since they learn by making mistakes. It should come as no surprise that neural networks only gained popularity when the majority of organizations embraced big data analytics and amassed massive data sets. The data used during the training stage must be labeled because the model's first few iterations entail educated estimates about the contents of an image or passages of speech. This is necessary so that the model can assess if its prediction was accurate. This implies that unstructured data is less helpful even if many big data firms have enormous volumes of data. Deep learning models cannot train on unstructured data, hence they can only interpret unstructured data once they have been trained and attain an acceptable level of accuracy.

2.4.2 Deep Learning use cases

Deep learning models can be used for a variety of tasks since they process information similarly to how the human brain does. The majority of image identification, natural language processing (NLP), and speech recognition software currently uses deep learning. These tools are starting to appear in many different applications, such as self-driving cars and interpreting services. All types

of big data analytics applications, such as those that concentrate on natural language processing (NLP), language translation, medical diagnosis, stock market trading signals, network security, and picture recognition, are currently covered by deep learning applications.

The following are some of the specific fields where deep learning is currently being used:

1) **Customer Experience (CX):** Deep learning algorithms are already utilized by chatbots. As deep learning develops, it is anticipated that it will be applied in many industries to enhance CX and boost customer satisfaction.

2) **Text Generation:** Machines are taught the grammar and style of a piece of writing and then use this model to automatically write an entirely new text that matches the original text's proper spelling, grammar, and style.

3) **Medical Research:** Cancer researchers have begun to incorporate deep learning into their practice in order to detect cancer cells automatically.

4) **Computer Vision:** Deep learning has considerably improved computer vision, allowing computers to do extremely accurate object identification, image classification, restoration, and segmentation.

2.4.3 Deep Learning Challenges

The most important limitation of deep learning models is the fact that they learn through observations. They therefore only have knowledge of the training data. The models won't learn in a generalizable way if a user only has a small amount of data or data from a single source that isn't necessarily representative of the greater functional area. Another major issue with deep learning systems is biases. A model will replicate similar biases in its predictions if it was trained on biased

data. Since models learn to differentiate based on minute variations in data items, deep learning programmers have had difficulty with this. The factors it determines to be important are frequently not explicitly expressed to the programmer. As an illustration, this means that without the programmer's awareness, a facial recognition algorithm might infer features about a person based on attributes like ethnicity or gender.

Hardware requirements for deep learning models could also place restrictions. Multicore high-performance graphics processing units (GPUs) and other comparable processing units are necessary to increase efficiency and decrease time consumption. However, these gadgets are expensive and energy-hungry. Hard disk drive (HDD) or RAM-based solid-state drive, as well as random access memory (SSD).

Fig 2.1 – Deep Learning as a subset of AI

2.5 Computer Vision

An interdisciplinary scientific topic called computer vision studies how advanced knowledge may be extracted by computers from digital images or films. From an engineering standpoint, it aims to comprehend and automate operations that the human visual system is capable of performing. The aim of computer vision issues is to use the observed image data to infer something about the outside environment on an abstract level (*Simon, 2012*).

The automatic extraction of data from images is known as computer vision. From 3D models, camera location, object identification and recognition, to grouping and searching visual content, information might refer to anything (*Erik, 2012*). There are many different uses for computer vision, both new and old (such as industrial inspection, mobile robot navigation, and military intelligence) (e.g., human computer interaction, image retrieval in digital libraries, medical image analysis, and the realistic rendering of synthetic scenes in computer graphics).

2.5.1 Uses of Computer Vision in Education

Computer vision analysis can be used to look into how students interact and behave throughout different group activities (*fig. 2.2*), as well as how they teach others and feel among their peers. Peer interaction among students is maximized when professors divide their class into groups according to how comfortable each student is. Instructors can assess user engagement levels by observing user behavior, eye movement, and posture using computer vision. This enables teachers to assess the conduct of their students and determine which sections were interesting to them and which bored them.

Computer vision can offer helpful insights into students' posture, face orientation, and gesticulation during team activities by recording all student interactions.

The following is a list of "affective computing" advancements being used in education:

- 1) Transdermal Optical Imaging: which uses a camera to detect face blood flow information and determine student moods in situations where visual signals are not readily available.
- 2) Electroencephalogram (EEG) electrical brain activity tests are used to assess pupils' emotional arousal, task performance, and to give individuals with computer mediation.
- 3) Wearable affective technology: such as a social-emotional intelligence prosthetic, that detects human affects in children in real time by using a small camera and analyzing facial expressions and head movements to infer the child's cognitive-affective state.
- 4) A glove-like gadget that tracks students' physiological arousal and monitors skin conductivity to determine how stimulated they are.
- 5) Emotionally intelligent computing systems that can analyze emotion and respond with appropriate expressions, allowing educators to give highly tailored content that inspires youngsters.

All of these advancements are part of the ongoing effort to turn "real-time mood monitoring" and "emotional feedback" gadgets into critical technology for understanding, measuring, and managing human emotions in modern society.

2.5.2 Computer Vision in Education and Privacy

The use of computer vision in education has been disputed and problematic. The morality of keeping children under continual observation has long been debated. Additionally, it's possible that the technology itself isn't yet prepared for general use. Computer vision facial recognition techniques are currently highly sensitive to errors, with women and people of color reporting

higher error rates. In the case of online courses, there is a great deal of debate around the volume of information and duration for which the website can track the user's movements. Face recognition data is obviously at considerable risk of being sold or compromised by a third party, as well as being utilized for other illegal activities. to name just a few.

Fig 2.2 – Uses of Computer Vision Analysis in Education (S Peng et al., 2021)

2.6 Facial Emotion Recognition System

Due to its focus on the core components of recognizing facial emotion expressions, FER is also known as facial emotion recognition. It involves recognizing expressions that convey fundamental emotions like fear, happiness, contempt, and so forth (Barlett, et al., 2003). This field has grown significantly as a result of the quick advancement of artificial intelligence techniques in fields like human-computer interaction (Dornaika et al., 2007); virtual reality (VR); Hickson et al., 2017; augment reality (AR); Assari et al., 2011; and others; because of its tremendous academic and

commercial potential, facial emotion recognition (FER) is an essential topic in the domains of computer vision and artificial intelligence.

2.6.1 Face Recognition

Face recognition technology is a significant research endeavor in the fields of pattern identification and computer vision because it has the potential to detect identities and other information based on the visual characteristics of a facial image. (*Zhao & Mei, 2017*). Face traits have the advantages of being good, straightforward, and practical when compared to other biological features; as a result, face recognition is more agreeable to users. The data capturing module, the feature extraction module, the classification module, and the training classifier database module are the four fundamental parts of a face recognition system.

2.6.2 Head Pose Estimation

Head pose estimation is the process of assisting biometric systems that make use of any of the biometric features of the head, including the face, ear, or iris (HPE). (*Andrea et al., 2022*). It is regarded as a preprocessing step to choose the best frame for face recognition in a video, as well as a behavioral feature to assess the subject's intent and a description to help frontalize the face. (*Andrea et al, 2022*). By observing the head's rotational angles, it accomplishes this. This specific biometric branch is used in areas (*fig 2.3*) such as optimal frame selection, facial frontalization, driver concentration detection, and surveillance for identification Finding the head posture orientation is the purpose of HPE (yaw, pitch, roll). The main steps of an HPE algorithm is summarized in the figure below (*fig 2.4*).

Fig 2.3 – Areas of application of HPE (Andrea et al., 2022)

Fig 2.4- HPE Framework (Andea et al., 2022)

2.6.3 Eye Gaze Measurement

Users' gazes and regions of interest from eye trackers have been utilized to understand the moods of learners while engaging in any educational activity in online learning.

To ascertain where the users were looking, (Aslan et al., 2014) used statistical facial traits, depth data, and eye tracker data. Nine pilot sessions of the decision trees, random forest, naive bayes, logistic regression, and multilayer perceptron machine learning algorithms were employed for testing.

Despite their efficiency, the fundamental challenge with eye-tracking-based approaches is precise ocular calibration. For these techniques to give accurate data, each participant must undergo many

calibration rounds. Studies must typically omit participants who wear glasses or have eye disorders due to calibration concerns (*Raina et al. 2016*). Limiting participant mobility to stay within the eye-tracker range is a substantial challenge as well, although doing so is impractical in a real-world educational context.

2.6.4 Hand-Over-Face Gestures in Learning and Teaching

The majority of research on learning and teaching relies on the use of facial expressions as the primary method of emotional communication, despite the fact that (*Gelder 2006*) claims there are similarities between how the brain reacts to emotional body languages and how expressions are identified.

The hand over face gesture was studied by (*Whitehill et al., 2014*) as one of the faces of interaction. The hand-over-face description, hand motion on the face, and the area occluded by the hand over the face, according to (*Mahmoud et al., 2016*) are key nonverbal communication channels that significantly reveal a person's cognitive state. Hands over Face gestures (*fig 2.5*) can amplify the affective cues conveyed by facial expressions, rather than being redundant information. In everyday interactions and conversations, we routinely use our hands to convey nonverbal messages (*Rautaray and Agrawal 2015*), ranging from simple movements like pointing to objects to more complicated ones like expressing emotions. We tend to put our hands closer to our faces, which are often partially veiled and can be used as a key to determine our emotional states, more often. (*Tofighi et al., 2016*) also identified disengagement, attention, intention, and actions using hand gestures (DAIA). Different levels of hand speed, raising the hands above the waist, and other hand movements can all be detected using the binary classifiers in DAIA. These classifiers identify the action-taking intent of the user. Finally, by examining the classifiers' judgments, a Finite State

Transducer (FST) of engagement detection was employed to flow between various emotional states.

Fig 2.5- Common Hand-over-face gestures (Pease and Pease (2006))

2.7 Student Engagement Systems

Many different facets of learners' engagements have been examined in the literature (*Bosch 2016; Fredrick et al. 2004; Anderson et al. 2004*). (*Bosch 2016*) divides engagement into three categories: emotive, behavioral, and cognitive. In contrast to (*Fredrick et al.,2004*) who defined engagement as being behavioral, cognitive, and emotional, (*Anderson et al.,2004*) described it as being academic, behavioral, cognitive, and psychological.

Affective engagement refers to the emotional attitude, such as being interested in a topic and enjoying learning about it, whereas academic engagement refers to academic identification (such as getting along with teachers) and participation (such as spending time on tasks, not skipping classes) towards learning (*Bosch et al., 2016*). The idea of behavioral engagement is built on involvement, which involves engaging in extracurricular and classroom activities, staying focused, completing assignments on time, and paying attention to directions from the instructor (*Christenson et al., 2012*). Cognitive engagement is the thought and willingness to put up the work needed to understand difficult topics and develop difficult abilities, such as heightened focus, memory, and creative thinking (*Anderson et al., 2004*). Emotional engagement includes both

favorable and unfavorable reactions to teachers, students, and academic success (*Fredrick et al., 2004*). Examples of psychological engagement include connections with teachers, peers, and a sense of belonging.

2.7.1 Engagement Estimation Methods

We categorize the present systems into three broad groups: automatic, semi-automatic, and manual, taking into account the methods' reliance on student engagement.

The approaches in each category are then subdivided (*fig. 2.6*) based on the types of data they employ, such as audio, video, learner log data, etc. Computer vision based methods in the automatic category are specifically looked at because they show promise in an online learning setting, are unobtrusive, and are cost-effective when taking into account the hardware and software needed for gathering and analyzing video data.

The manual methods now include self-reporting and observational check-list categories. The methods utilized in engagement tracing are semi-automatic. The automatic approaches in this area are further classified into computer vision-based methods, methods that analyze sensor data, and methods that analyze log files depending on the data that these methods process for engagement detection. The computer vision-based methods are further separated into three sub-categories: eye movement, gestures and postures, and the modalities they use for engagement detection. The aforementioned modalities are used singly in some research projects, while others think that combining two or more of them to boost accuracy has potential.

2.7.1.1 Manual Method

The manual category covers engagement detection methods that call for active participation from learners. In the manual category, self-reporting is a popular strategy where learners use a series of questions to self-report their degree of focus, distraction, enthusiasm, or boredom.

Self-reporting is of significant interest to many academics because it is straightforward to administer and provides some useful information regarding learner involvement. For instance, it is useful to know that between 25% and 60% of students' report being bored or disinterested (*Shernoff et al., 2000*). However, a variety of factors outside the researchers' control, such as the students' candor, willingness to disclose their emotions, and the correctness of their evaluation of their emotions, will determine whether the results from the self-reporting are genuine (*D'Mello et al., 2014*).

2.7.1.2 Semi-Automatic Methods

In the semi-automatic category, learners must indirectly participate in the engagement detection step (*Dewan et al., 2019*). Semi-automatic techniques of gauging engagement also include physiologically based methods and knowledge tracing. Knowledge tracing places a heavy duty on the tutor since they must gauge the level of student engagement by looking at how they respond to the questions that are posed to them. In order to interpret physiological signals like brain signals, heart signals, etc., wearable devices like electro dermal activity sensors are used in the aspect of measuring engagement using physiological approaches (*Di Lascio et al., 2018*). However, this approach is pricy and intrusive to the wearer.

2.7.1.3 Automatic Methods

The automatic category of techniques extracts characteristics from a range of traits captured by image sensors (such as gaze, facial gestures, gestures, and postures), biological and neurological sensors (such as heart rate, EEG, blood pressure, or galvanic skin response), or by monitoring students' activities in their learning environments (*Dewan et al., 2019*). (such as total time spent studying, number of forum posts, average length of time to solve a problem, number of submissions correct, etc.). These methods automatically extract features without interfering with the way that students are motivated to learn.

Computer vision-based methods (*D'Mello et al. 2009; D'Mello and Graesser 2010; Kapoor and Picard 2007*) offer a variety of ways to measure learners' involvement by looking at cues from movements and postures, eye movement, and facial expressions. Computer vision-based systems' primary advantages are their simplicity and absence of interference with the learning process, which is comparable to how a teacher can observe a student's motivation in class without interfering with his or her actions. Because they are valuable in large offline classrooms, this study will analyze computer-based automated methods for evaluating student engagement.

Fig 2.6 – Taxonomy of Learner’s engagement detection methods (Dewan et al., 2019)

2.8 Related Works

The ability of students to direct their own learning inside and outside of the classroom has long been a heated topic for discussion among educational scholars, legislators, and practitioners. The "one-size-fits-all" attitude of industrial society serves as the foundation for the contemporary educational systems (Watson et al. 2015). Numerous studies have been conducted over the years to improve the effectiveness of the learning environment in the classroom by simulating students' emotions and behaviors.

In lieu of exploring the combination of hand-over-gestures with facial expressions, (Gunavathi & Siddappa, 2018) developed a multimodal system for cognitive state recognition. They achieved this by splitting the methodology to three independent tasks which include coding and classifying hand-over-face descriptors, detection of basic facial expressions using facial landmarks and finally

combination of facial expressions and hand-over-face gestures for recognition of cognitive state. The system achieved an accuracy of 90.51%. The unique proposition of this system is that it is robust to variations in facial expressions, hand shapes, and occlusions. However, the study is limited to four facial expressions from the seven basic emotions which cannot be used to imply academic cognitive states in a learning environment.

As a step further to the work by *Gunavathi & Siddappa, 2018*, (*Ardhendu et al., 2020*) took the research on hand-over-face gestures by trying to understand and make inference students behaviors and its relationship to learning type. The aim of the study was not to associate a given hand-over-face gesture to an affective state, it was to measure the rate at which it occurs with respect to difficulty levels of topics. The study relied heavily on the automatic detection of seven basic emotions using an IntraFace tool. The research leveraged on this tool because of its high recognition performance. However, as elaborate and comprehensive this study is, it did not take into consideration multiple emotions that could occur simultaneously in a learning environment nor linked it with student engagement in the classroom.

Learning environment which can be offline or online posits different methodologies for detecting learner's engagement. In detecting in real-time the emotions of students via webcams, (*Bahreini & Westera, 2016*) developed a framework which is an extension of Face Tracker Software (*Saragih, Lucey, & Cohn, 2010*) to recognize, simulate and interpret emotions in real-time in an e-learning environment and in return provides appropriate feedback. The proposed system achieved an accuracy of 72%. However, the study could have been interesting to explore if the framework included the voice emotion recognition originally planned. We could have seen the effects on accuracy and learning if facial and voice emotions were combined.

Still on e-learning, researchers went a step further in estimating students' engagement; such work could be seen in a study by (Delgado et al., 2021). The study hoped to support students' emotions and also maintain student engagement for online learning. They developed a computer vision module that alerts wandering students to regain their attention, this module included state of the art deep learning image classifiers for head pose estimation. In addition to that, they made use of a learning platform known as MathSpring as a form of validation by including gaze baselines. One unique feature of this study is the attention-wandering which was implemented using eye tracking technique. It not just identifies distraction; it tries to identify what the student is paying attention to. Is the student looking at the screen or paper or is the student just wandering away? The end result of this study is a comprehensive engagement video dataset that has been annotated with time series information about head pose.

Taking head pose and eye gaze research a bit further, and also incorporating some specific emotions, (Krithika l., et al 2016), developed a system that recognizes and monitors students' emotions in an e-learning environment and gives a real-time feedback on students' concentration levels. The concentration levels were grouped into three levels such as High Concentration, Medium Concentration and Low Concentration. Emotions such as excitement, boredom, yawning, drowsiness, abnormal head and eyes movements were used to predict concentration levels. The focus of the research was on abnormal head rotation of a student learning online. The implementation of the system was done on Matlab using Viola Jones and Local Binary Pattern methods. However, during testing the duration was too small to make a general feedback about the engagement of the students in the classroom.

In a study to measure students' engagement with an automated gaze system, (Bidwell and Fuchs 2011) designed a student engagement classifier using recorded videos taken in the classroom. A

face tracking system was used to extract the students' gazes. However due to a poor classification accuracy using the Hidden Markov Model, they were only able to classify whether a student is engaged or not.

Emotion analysis was taken to the next level in a research conducted by (Zeng *et al.*, 2019) in which they designed an interactive visualization system called EmotionCues that supports automatic emotion extraction and multi-level visual summarization from recorded classroom videos. The system through three major levels included an extensive analysis of the overall emotions of the students, individual-related characteristics and video analysis of the students. The analysis was not just for a single student, it included both the individual emotions and the emotion trends as a group. In addition to that, a front-end web-based system was implemented to support the visualization using Vue and Flask. Nonetheless, the visualization style could have been better improved, there were situations where a stacked bar chart could have worked better in place of a pie chart. Head pose could have further been included to better understand students' emotion status in the classroom.

Offline classroom introduces its own dynamics when trying to incorporate an automatic visual system into the environment. (Zaletelj and Kosir 2017) estimated students' attention in an offline classroom environment using non-verbal cues. They developed a model with extracted 2D and 3D features from the Kinect One Camera using machine learning algorithms like decision trees and k-nearest neighbors. They achieved a test accuracy of 75.3% which was then tested against the ground-truth attention levels by human annotations. The analysis was restricted to only six students rather than the whole classroom.

(Soloviev, 2018) presented a system to continuously analyze visual data streams from classroom cameras by classifying students' facial expressions into positive and negative emotions. A boosted

decision tree method was used in training their model which resulted in an accuracy of 84.80%. However, this study did not put into consideration students' academic emotions while classifying their engagement levels.

In a research conducted by (*Alkabbany, et al., 2019*), they proposed a novel framework that measures students' engagement levels either in a class environment or an e-learning environment. Face tracking is done through the video frames captured in the user's video. Different features such as eye gaze, head pose, facial fiducial points are extracted from the user's face and are used to detect the Facial Action Coding System (FACS) which then are used to measure students' emotional engagement.

The research conducted by (*Chen, et al 2019*) introduces a multi-camera-based emotion detection system in a classroom environment. The system is able to detect and record changes in students' facial expression and report to the teacher in real time. They combined three methodologies (Viola Jones, Gabor Wavelet, and Multi-Layer Perceptron) to dynamically recognize the students' basic emotions in real time.

In a study by (*Ashwin and Gudetti 2019*), they proposed a system that classifies engagement into one of the four engagement levels, that is high, medium, low or no engagement levels. They trained an anchor-based detection framework using Convolutional Neural Network-based architecture using a self-created classroom student behavioral dataset. However, the system proposed does not emphasize on facial emotion analysis.

(*Luo et al., 2020*) used a 3D model that makes use of head pose, smiling facial expression, and smartphones to estimate student interest in classroom settings. The trained model includes

hierarchical and conditional random forest algorithms in the student attention estimation system. However, this study is expensive because physical devices are needed to get interactive data.

(Zheng, R. et al., 2020) identified students' engagement by analyzing behaviors detected from the students. They trained an improved Faster R-CNN model on the created classroom students' behavioral dataset consisting of hand raising, standing and sleeping behaviors. However, this study is constrained to only students' behaviors with no room for academic-based emotions for estimating students' engagement.

In the study conducted by (Ardhendu Behera et al., 2020), they carried out a detailed quantitative analysis of body-part movements and gestures/emotions change over time, learning types and the difficulty of the learning topics and how it can be linked to students' engagements in the classroom using a state-of-the-art IntraFace tool. They explored the variety of nonverbal behaviors (emotions, head movements, head pose, eye gaze, *hand-over-face* (HoF) gestures), to recognize students' affective states in real-time using state-of-the-art deep models trained on ImageNet dataset.

Multi-modal analytics went a step higher in a research conducted by (Peng et al., 2021) where they monitored students' mental states (boredom, frustration, concentration, and confusion) during classroom discussions. They developed an intelligent multi-sensor system using modalities such as facial, heart rate and acoustic indicators. They trained a set of machine learning algorithms such as support vector machine, random forest and multilayer perceptron using features from facial, heart rate and auditory modalities. However, the implementation of this study is expensive because it needs physical devices such as Apple Watch, Air pods to measure student's multi-modality data which is costly for large offline classroom setting.

(Vanneste et al., 2021) assessed students' engagement in the offline classroom by recognizing their classroom actions using body pose. They trained a deep learning action classifier with the dataset

of eight classroom actions like hand-raising, hands-on-face, etc. However, just like most study, this study is limited to just behavioral cues and not academic-affective cues in estimating students' engagement.

In a study by (Pabba and Kumar 2022), they developed a vision-based automated system for student group engagement in a large offline classroom environment by analyzing students' academic affective states through facial expression. The facial expression dataset used was created from a classroom lecture video frames of more than forty students. A convolutional Neural Network-based architecture was used as the framework for the recognition system.

Table 2.1 Literature Review Table

Works	Methodology	Outcome	Limitation
Pabba and Kumar, (2022)	Academic affective states dataset was trained using a convolutional neural network to build a facial expression recognition model	They detected student group engagement by analyzing academic affective states such as boredom, frustration, confusion, focus, sleepy, yawning.	The facial recognition algorithm was not robust enough to include body gestures.
Vanneste et al., (2021)	They trained a deep learning action classifier with the dataset of eight classroom actions like	They assessed students' engagement in the offline classroom by recognizing their classroom actions using body pose.	this study is limited to just behavioral cues and not academic-affective cues in estimating students' engagement

	hand-raising, hands-on-face		
Ardhendu et al., (2020)	They explored the variety of nonverbal behaviors (emotions, head movements, head pose, eye gaze, <i>hand-over-face</i> (HoF) gestures) using IntraFace tool	They recognized students' affective states in real-time using state-of the-art deep models trained on ImageNet dataset	High dependence on a tool as the main framework for the facial recognition module.
Peng et al., (2021)	They trained a set of machine learning algorithms such as support vector machine, random forest and multilayer perceptron using features from facial, heart rate and auditory modalities	they monitored students' mental states (boredom, frustration, concentration, and confusion) during classroom discussions	the implementation of this study is expensive because it needs physical devices.
Zheng et al., (2020)	They trained an improved Faster R-CNN model on the created classroom students' behavioral dataset consisting of hand	They identified students' engagement by analyzing behaviors detected from the students	This study is constrained to only students' behaviors with no room for academic-based

	raising, standing and sleeping behaviors		emotions for estimating students' engagement
Chen, et al (2019)	They combined three methodologies (Viola Jones, Gabor Wavelet, and Multi-Layer Perceptron) to dynamically recognize the students' basic emotions in real time.	They introduced a multi-camera-based emotion detection system in a classroom environment to detect and record changes in students' facial expression and report to the teacher in real time.	The study only focused on the basic emotions and not the learning-specific emotions in the classroom.
Zeng et al., 2019	A front-end web-based visualization system was implemented to support the emotion analysis using Vue and Flask frameworks.	they designed an interactive visualization system called EmotionCues that supports automatic emotion extraction and multi-level visual summarization from recorded classroom videos.	Choice of visualization style for emotion trend analysis was tacky.
Klein and Celik (2017)	Transfer learning was performed on Alexnet using synthesized dataset	The study categorized attention levels into interested or not interested.	In estimation student engagement, academic affective states were not considered

	of popular classroom actions and postures.		
Zaletelj and Kosir (2017)	Extracted 2D and 3D features were used to train decision tree and KNN algorithms	Attention levels were classified into high, medium and low.	The proposed system cannot work in a large offline classroom due to the fact that the Kinect sensor has a short range of imaging system.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This chapter dwells more on describing the process, methods and tools that will be used to achieve the objectives of the study as earlier stated. A software process model is an abstraction of the software development process. It can be seen as a representation of the order of activities of the process and the sequence in which they are performed. The goal is to provide guidance for controlling and coordinating the tasks to achieve the end product and objectives as effectively as possible.

In this chapter, the concept of software process model and Software Development Life Cycle will be discussed; its methods and phases inclusive, existing and proposed frameworks will also be discussed and finally Unified Modeling Language which is a language for describing the model of a system along with the use case and static model will also be discussed.

3.1 Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC)

A process that defines the various stages involved in the development of software for delivering high-quality product is referred to as Software Development Life Cycle. It covers the entire lifecycle of a software, that is from inception to retirement of the product. The framework or diagrammatic representation of the SDLC is shown in fig 3.1.

SDLC provides a well-structured flow of phases that help an organization to quickly produce high-quality software which is well-tested and ready for production use. SDLC being a repetitive methodology, one has to ensure code quality at every cycle to remove typical pitfalls of software

development project. It works by lowering the cost of software development while simultaneously improving quality and shortening production time.

The process model used for the research work is a prescriptive software model in which activities and tasks occur sequentially with defined guidelines for progress. The model allows a choice of framework activities that is necessary to achieve the complexity of any software project.

Fig 3.1-SDLC Framework

3.1.1 Requirement Gathering and Analysis Phase

Gathering requirements for a project is the most important part of SDLC. In this phase, the expectations of the project are stated, including those who will use the system, how the system will be used, and what is expected of the system's functionalities. When the requirements are stated, the analysis of each requirement starts to check for its feasibility and to ensure the requirements can be included in the software without causing breaks or problems in the system functionality. The requirements for EmoAI Smart Classroom was elicited through extensive review of existing systems.

The system requirements are:

1. The system should be able to extract academic affective states and hands-over-face gestures to five overall emotions- engaged, boredom, frustrated, confusion, and distracted
2. From the emotion analysis, the system should be able to classify students' engagement into High, Medium and Low.
3. Lecturers should be able to sign up and log in to the system.
4. Lecturers should be able to upload pre-recorded classroom video
5. Lecturers should be able to see the engagement analysis of the class as a whole.
6. Students should be able to sign up and login
7. Students should be able to register their faces in the database.
8. The visualization web app should be flexible, usable, operable by an experienced user.

3.1.2 System Design

After requirement gathering phase, the next phase on the process model is the system design. The list of requirements developed in the definition phase is used to make design choices. One or more designs are created to achieve the project result. Depending on the project, the design phase could include diagrams, flowcharts, sketches, prototypes, screen designs, Unified Modeling Language (UML) Schemas, etc. In the design phase, we move from a requirements specification to a design specification and decisions made at this level will affect the success of software construction.

The system design stage consists of four distinct stages which can be carried out in no particular order; these stages are Data design, Interface design, Architecture design and Component design.

1. Data design which involves determining how data will be organized, stored, maintained, updated, accessed and used.
2. Interface design which involves designing an overall user interface; including screens, commands, controls, and features that enable users to interact with an application.
3. Architecture design which determines client/server interaction, network configuration, internet/intranet interface issues and communication mechanism between components.
4. Component Design which determines the processing strategies and how business process can be refined into algorithms that can easily be converted to program codes.

In the design of this project, an object oriented modeling approach is taken into consideration. Implementation will be done using an Object oriented programming language.

3.1.2.1 Unified Modeling Language (UML)

Unified Modeling Language was created to forge a common visual language in the complex world of software development that would also be understandable for business users and anyone who wants to understand a system. UML diagrams describe the boundary, structure, and the behavior of the system and the objects within it.

The UML diagrams used to model this project are; Use case diagram, Activity diagram, Class Diagram, Sequence Diagram, state machine diagram and a proposed framework for the EmoAI Smart Classroom.

3.1.2.2 System Framework

The system framework is often a layered structure that indicates the type of program to be built and how they would interrelate. System framework serves as a blueprint for how the component of the system is arranged in realizing the functionality of the system.

The existing framework as proposed by (*Pabba and Kumar, 2021*) is shown in *fig 3.2*. This framework talked about analyzing student engagement levels into medium, low and high using two separate but complementary modules known as the offline and online modules. The offline module is a trained Convolutional Neural Network-based Facial Emotion Recognition Model while the online module uses the model in the offline module to estimate in real-time student engagement levels. The flowchart is shown in *fig 3.4*.

In contrary to the existing framework, a new emotional and behavioral student engagement is proposed as seen in *fig 3.3*. Adjustment is made to the offline module by introducing a YOLO V8-based Hand-over-face recognition model for identification of the learning behaviors of the students in the classroom. Furthermore, in the Pabba and Kumar Model, adjustment is made to the post-

processing module by including a visualization module in addition to the engagement level graph of individual students in the classroom. The flowchart is shown in *fig 3.5*

This new framework specifies an integration of the subsystems in the existing framework and an addition of a new subsystem to allow for an improved recognition accuracy of student engagement in the classroom to improve classroom teaching experience.

The EmoAI Smart Classroom proposed framework is in three major stages which is further broken down into sub-stages: which will be briefly explained.

[1.] Dataset Construction

Public dataset will be used for the data repository. DAiSEE dataset is a public dataset that consists of students' facial expressions in an E-learning environment. The affective states contained in the dataset are boredom, confusion, engagement, and frustration.

[2.] YOLO V8 Object Detection Architecture (You Only Look Once)

YOLO is a state-of-the-art algorithm that uses an end-to-end neural network that makes predictions of bounding boxes and class probabilities all at once. It performs all of its predictions with the help of a single fully connected layer.

The algorithm takes an image as input and uses simple deep convolutional neural network to detect objects in the image. It introduces a loss function and processes images at higher resolutions making it suitable for detecting smaller objects.

[3.] Offline Module

i. Video Acquisition

In the video acquisition process, the lecturer uploads classroom videos of interest; The video format of the video streams is mp4 or MOV, and finally the video data is stored

in a database or a file system for future analysis and improvement of the engagement detection system. The storage format should be chosen based on the requirements of the engagement detection system, such as the storage capacity, data retrieval speed, and data security.

ii. Pre-Processing

The first step in preprocessing is to detect the faces of the students in the video streams. This was done using a face detection algorithm known as HOG-based face detection. After the faces have been detected, the next step is to align them so that the facial features can be consistently extracted and analyzed. This was done using OpenCV, a deep learning-based method. After the faces have been aligned, they can be cropped and resized to a consistent size for further processing. The next step is important to ensure that the facial features are extracted accurately and consistently. To ensure that the facial features are extracted accurately and consistently, the images were subjected to histogram equalization to adjust the brightness and contrast of the images. The final step in preprocessing is to normalize the data so that the features can be consistently extracted and analyzed. This was done by transforming the images to a standard size, format, and color space

iii. Student Affective Classification

At this stage, the dataset gotten from a combination of facial expressions and body posture were labeled with their corresponding affective state categories; The model was trained on the extracted features and the corresponding affective state categories using an appropriate optimization algorithm. The performance of the

trained model was evaluated using appropriate performance metrics, such as precision, recall, on a separate validation dataset. The trained and validated model was deployed as a web app to enable real-time affective state classification.

iv. Visualization

The engagement scores computed from the post-processing stage are displayed in real-time on a monitor for the teacher showing the details of each student which includes their attention analysis and their engagement analysis.

Fig 3.2—Proposed Framework by Pabba and Kumar (2021)

Fig 3.3—System Framework

Fig 3.4 Proposed Framework flowchart (Pabba and Kumar, 2021)

Fig 3.5 System Flowchart

3.1.2.3 Use Case Diagram

Use case diagrams model the behavior of a system and help to capture the requirements of the system. A use case diagram summarizes the details of your system's users and their interaction with the system. With the help of a use case diagram, the scope of a system can be defined, possible scenarios in which a system can interact with the people can be shown and finally the goals of the actors can be achieved.

The use case diagram was employed in modeling the EmoAI Smart Classroom as shown in fig 3.6. There are three actors in the use case model, these actors are: System administrator, Student and Lecturer. Each actor can perform different use case (actions) depending on their privilege on the system. The system administrator is often able to perform all use case.

3.1.2.4 Activity Diagram

Activity diagram is a behavioral diagram in UML Diagram that describes the dynamic aspects of the system. It describes how activities are coordinated to provide a service which can be at different levels of abstraction.

Like a flowchart, it visually presents a series of actions or flow of control in a system.

An activity diagram for a student engagement detection system in a large offline classroom might include the following steps:

- Start: The system is activated by uploading of classroom video
- Face Detection: The system uses computer vision algorithms to detect the faces of students in the classroom.

- **Attention Tracking:** The system tracks the attention level of each student by analyzing their facial expressions and body poses.
- **Engagement Assessment:** The system assesses the level of engagement of each student based on their attention level and other factors, such as the length of time they have been engaged and the level of interaction with the lecture or material.
- **Record Data:** The system records the data on student engagement and stores it for later analysis.
- **Generate Reports:** The system generates reports on student engagement, including the average engagement level for each class, the number of students who are engaged, and the distribution of engagement levels across the class.
- **Notify Instructor:** The system notifies the instructor if the engagement level of a student falls below a predetermined threshold. This might be beyond the scope of this thesis.
- **Stop:** The system stops after analysis has been done.

The activity diagram of EmoAI Smart Classroom is shown in fig 3.7.

Fig 3.6—Use case diagram for EmoAI Smart Classroom

Fig—3.7 Activity Diagram for EmoAI Smart Classroom

3.1.2.5 Class Diagram

A class diagram describes the structure of a system by showing the system's classes, their attributes, operations, and relationships among the objects. The model is often used to construct the code used in the implementation of the system. The explanation of drawing the EmoAI is shown below:

Class: Student

Attributes: name, studentID, engagementScore

Methods: getName(), getStudentID(), getEngagementScore(), setEngagementScore(score)

Class: Lecturer

Attributes: name, lecturerID

Methods: getName(), getlecturerID(), viewEngagementAnalysis(), viewAttentionAnalysis()

Class: Classroom

Attributes: classroomID, studentList

Methods: addStudent(student), removeStudent(student), getStudentList(), getClassroomID()

Class: VideoProcessor

Attributes: videoStream

Methods: startCapture(), stopCapture(), processVideo(), getVideoStream()

Class: EngagementDetector

Attributes: videoProcessor, audioProcessor, engagementScores

Methods: processData(), calculateEngagementScores(), getEngagementScores(),
setEngagementScores(scores)

Class: ReportGenerator

Attributes: classroom, engagementScores

Methods: generateReport(), getReport(), getClassroom(), getEngagementScores()

Class: Database

Attributes: data

Methods: storeData(data), retrieveData(query), updateData(data)

The class diagram in fig 3.8 shows the static structure of the EmoAI Smart Classroom which comprises of different classes such as: Face Recognizer, Engagement Detector, etc., There are also representation of relationship such as inheritance, aggregation and association between the classes.

Fig 3.8—Class Diagram of EmoAI Smart Classroom

3.1.2.6 Sequence Diagram

A sequence diagram shows object interactions arranged in time sequence. It depicts the objects and classes involved in the scenario and the sequence of messages exchanged between the objects needed to carry out the functionality of the scenario. They are always associated with use case realization.

A sequence diagram for a student engagement detection system in a large offline classroom could be as follows:

- **System Initialization:** A teacher starts a lecture and triggers the student engagement detection system by pressing a button on a remote control.
- **Class Start:** The system captures the video input from multiple cameras placed in the classroom and starts processing the data.
- **Attention Tracking:** The video data is analyzed in real-time to identify and track the faces of the students and to extract features such as gaze direction, head position, and facial expressions.
- **Student Engagement Detection:** The extracted features are used to compute the engagement scores of each student. The engagement scores are based on factors such as attention, interest, and participation in the lecture.
- **Visualization:** The engagement scores are displayed in real-time on a monitor for the teacher. The teacher can use the information to make adjustments to their teaching style and content to improve student engagement.
- **Engagement Feedback:** At the end of the lecture, the system generates a report that summarizes the engagement levels of the students during the lecture. The report can be

used by the teacher to provide feedback to the students and to track their progress over time.

- Storage: The system stores the video and audio data along with the engagement scores in a database for future analysis and improvement.

Fig 3.9—Sequence Diagram of EmoAI Smart Classroom.

CHAPTER FOUR

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION AND EVALUATION

4.1 Introduction

This chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the system implementation at both the model and interface levels. It encompasses the computer vision aspect, describing the tasks involved in developing the system and outlining the necessary resources for successful implementation. The system implementation is the process that involves acquiring the necessary software resources and the evaluation of the system so as to eliminate any observed bugs.

The following subsections will dive more into the resources and processes involved in the development of the engagement system.

4.2 Implementation at Model Level

This section talks about the tools and processes involved in building the machine learning model from the data collection to deployment (*see fig 4.1*). It leverages object detection techniques and utilizes YOLOV8 architecture to identify and classify the affective states of the students. The code for the computer vision computing was written in python programming language and the following are the steps involved:

Fig 4.1 Implementation at Model Level

4.2.1 The DAiSEE Dataset

DAiSEE (Dataset for Affective States in E-Environment) is the first multi-label video classification dataset comprising 9,068 video snippets captured from 112 users for recognizing user affective states of boredom, confusion, engagement, and frustration “in the wild”. The dataset has four levels of labels namely-very low, low, high and very high for each of the affective states.

Why DAiSEE?

The unique features of DAiSEE which made it desirable for this project are highlighted below:

- It is the first publicly available dataset for studying user engagement and related affective states in the wild.
- While there has been substantial work in recognition of the seven basic emotions, DAiSEE presents a dataset to understand subtler states such as engagement and boredom which are often not exhibited explicitly on a human.
- It contains videos, thus allowing researchers to use the temporal information for effective recognition.

4.2.2 Data Collection

DAiSEE was made available by Paper With Code through the link below:

<https://people.iith.ac.in/vineethnb/resources/daisee/index.html>

4.2.3 Frame Extraction

Frame extraction is the process of capturing individual frames or images from a video sequence. Since videos are essentially a sequence of frames that are displayed rapidly one after another creating the illusion of motion.

In order to capture the temporal changes in affect, a tool known as FFMPEG was used to extract frames at 30 frames per second (30fps). The frames extracted from the video (9,068) totaled to 2,723,882.

4.2.4 Data Annotation

Data annotation involves labeling data to show the outcome one wants the machine learning model to predict. This is an important step because without data annotation, every image extracted will look the same to the machine. Annotated data reveals features that will train the algorithm to identify the same features in data that has not been annotated.

Semi-Manual annotation using Label Assist was done on Roboflow (*see fig 4.2*). 707 images from the frames were loaded into the Annotation section of RoboFlow, and bounding boxes were drawn on the area of interest to map each affective state detected on the face to a label. One new label was added in addition to the four labels of interested. Hence the faces were mapped against five labels which are: “Engaged, confused, frustrated, distracted, bored.”

Fig 4.2 Annotation on RoboFlow (Roboflow.inc)

4.2.5 Model Building

- **Data Split**

To prepare the dataset for modeling, the data was split into train, test and validation sets. The splitting ratio used is 70-20-10. The general Kaggle convention could have also been used, however, the RoboFlow convention was used.

- **Data Pre-Processing**

To further prepare the dataset for modeling, the following techniques were used to enhance the quality and suitability of the input data (see fig 4.3) for the detection model:

- i. **Grayscale Conversion:** The images were converted to grayscale to reduce the color information and to make it easier for the model to focus on object shapes and edges.
- ii. **Resizing:** The images were resized to a consistent resolution (624x624) to maintain uniformity in the input data. Doing this makes it easier for the model to learn and generalize across different objects.
- iii. **Auto-Orient Correction:** The images were made to have the same orientation (portrait). This helps the model learn object features consistently without being confused by variations in rotation.
- iv. **Bounding Box Brightness Adjustments:** To enhance the visibility of the images to detect, the brightness of the regions within the bounding boxes were adjusted to 70% to make it easier for the model to detect images accurately.

Fig 4.3 (Result of the pre-processing steps) (Roboflow.inc)

- **Model Training**

The object detection model was trained by building upon the foundation of a pre-trained YOLO v8 architecture. The pre-trained model's weights were fine-tuned on the pre-processed dataset. During training, the dataset was fed into the model which learns to refine its internal features and parameters. The iterative optimization process, guided by loss functions and backpropagation, enabled the model to adapt to the nuances of the specific objects in the dataset.

The training took an hour (1hr) for it to be completed and for class loss results (see fig 4.4) to be generated.

- **Evaluation Metrics**

To assess the performance of the object detection model, the following metrics were used and the results are indicated as follows:

- i. **Mean Average Precision (mAP):** Mean Average Precision is a measure that evaluates the accuracy of object detection by considering both precision and recall. It computes the average precision across different levels of confidence thresholds for object detection.

The model recorded **65.3% mAP** which indicates that on the average, the model's predicted object bounding boxes are correct for about 65.3% of the objects in the dataset.

- ii. **Precision:** Precision is the ratio of true positive predictions (correctly detected objects) to the total number of positive predictions made by the model.

The model recorded **74.5% precision** which indicates that out of all the objects the model predicted as positive, approximately 74.5% were actually correct.

- iii. **Recall:** It is also known as sensitivity or true positive rate. It measures the model's ability to correctly detect a certain percentage of all the actual objects in the dataset. The model recorded **60.6% recall** which means the model was able to detect around 60.6% of all the actual objects present in the dataset.

Fig 4.4 Class loss results (*Roboflow.inc*)

- **Model Deployment**

The model was deployed on Roboflow where the functionality was tested through uploading of a classroom video. The result is shown in the figure below (see fig4.5).

Fig 4.5 Screenshot of an uploaded classroom video (Roboflow.inc)

4.3 Tools Used

The following are the tools used in the building, training, and deploying the machine learning model of this project:

1. Google Colab

It is a cloud-based Jupyter notebook environment provided by Google. It allows one to write and execute Python code in a collaborative and interactive manner. Colab provides access to GPUs and TPUs for accelerating computations, making it popular for training machine learning environment models.

2. Visual Studio Code

It is a widely used code editor developed by Microsoft. It provides extensions available for various frameworks, including machine learning libraries, making it a versatile choice for ML model development.

3. RoboFlow

It is a platform that helps streamline the process of managing, annotating, and preparing image and video data for machine learning. It provides tools to preprocess, augment, and export datasets, making it easier to train computer vision models like object detection or image segmentation.

4. Python

It is a popular and versatile programming language widely used in machine learning and data science. It offers a rich ecosystem of libraries and frameworks like TensorFlow, PyTorch, Scikit-learn, and more making it an essential tool for implementing machine learning models.

5. FFMPEG

It is a powerful multimedia framework that allows one process and manipulate audio and video files. FFMPEG is used in machine learning for tasks like converting video formats, extracting frames from videos for training data or preprocessing video data before feeding it into a model.

6. MediaPipe

It is an open-source library that provides customizable building blocks for various media processing tasks including facial recognition, pose estimation, and hand tracking.

4.4 Implementation at Design Level

This section talks about the tools and processes involved in designing and coding the visual elements and interactive components that allow users interact with the software and achieve their tasks (see fig 4.6). This implementation is concerned with the front-end or client-side development.

Fig 4.6 Implementation at Design Level

4.4.1 Functional Requirements

The following are the functional requirements of the web application:

- i. The system should be able to identify the emotions of the students
- ii. The system should be able to generate report on the student's engagement
- iii. Students/lecturers should be able to signup/log in to the system
- iv. Students should be able to upload their face images
- v. Lecturers should be able to upload classroom videos
- vi. Lectures should be able to view engagement analysis.

4.4.2 User Interface Prototype

This is the mockup of the software application's user interface. Figma as a tool was used in creating the visual representation of the different elements of the web application. The following are the different screens involved:

- **Splash Screen**

This is the home page of EmoAI, where students and lecturers can sign up or login and perform the necessary activities on the webapp

Fig 4.7 Splash Screen

- **Student Sign Up Page**

This is the signup page for students, where students can register with the school email address, full name, matric no and password

Welcome to EmoAI
Create an account or [log in](#)

School Email Address

Full Name

Matric No

Password

I agree to the privacy terms of EmoAI

[Sign Up](#)

Fig 4.8-Student Sign Up Page

- **Student Log-In Page**

Students log in with their matric no and password

Log in.

Enter your Matric No

Enter your Password

Log In

Fig 4.9-Student Log-In Page

- **Lecturer Sign Up**

This is the register page of lecturers where lecturers fill in their details such as the department, registration no, full name and password.

Welcome to EmoAI

Create an account or **log in**

Full Name

Department

Lecturer Registration No

Password

I agree to the privacy terms of EmoAI

Sign Up

Fig 4.10-Lecturer Sign Up

- **Lecturer Log In**

Lecturers log in with their registration number and password

The image shows a login interface for lecturers. On the left, there is a dark red vertical banner with a white silhouette of a person standing behind a podium with a laptop. The laptop screen displays a white padlock icon. To the right of the banner, the text "Log in." is displayed in a bold, black font. Below this, there are two input fields. The first is labeled "Enter your Reg No" and the second is labeled "Enter your Password". Both labels are in a standard black font. Below the password field, there is a rounded rectangular button with the text "Log In" inside.

Fig 4.11 Lecturer-Log In

- **Lecturer-Classroom Video Upload**

This is where lecturers upload pre-recorded classroom videos to get the engagement analysis

Fig 4.12-Video Upload

- **Lecturer-Engagement Analysis**

This is where lecturers get to see the engagement analysis of the students.

Fig 4.13 –Engagement Analysis

4.5 Workflow of the Integration of the Model and User Interface

The following are the steps taken to connect the model with the interface. The interface that was built was the lecturer's part where the lecturer as an admin uploads the video to get an engagement analysis report.

Step 1: Developing the ML Model and API

1. First, the ML model is trained to effectively classify engagement levels in classroom videos, distinguishing between low, medium, and high engagement.
2. Next, an API endpoint is established within the backend infrastructure. This endpoint, created using a programming language like Python and frameworks such as Flask or FastAPI, exposes the ML model's classification capabilities.
3. The endpoint's functionality encompasses accepting uploaded classroom videos, performing any necessary preprocessing, and then passing the videos through the ML model. Subsequently, the endpoint returns the determined engagement classification, thus forming a bridge between the backend and the model.

Step 2: Setting Up Strapi CMS

1. To manage content, a Strapi CMS is installed and configured on the server. This involves defining requisite content types and corresponding fields. One key content type, labeled "Video," includes fields like title, and a mechanism for uploading video files.
2. Role-based permissions are tailored to allow lecturers to upload videos, while administrators can oversee content management.

3. In the Strapi CMS, a webhook or server function is implemented to activate whenever a new video is uploaded. This function serves to connect with the ML model's API endpoint, passing the uploaded video for engagement classification. The obtained classification report and video details are subsequently stored in the Strapi database.

Step 3: Developing the Next.js Front End

1. The process begins by configuring a Next.js project for the frontend.
2. A user-friendly interface is crafted, enabling lecturers to seamlessly upload classroom videos. Within this interface, user-friendly form components are integrated, facilitating video detail input and file uploads.
3. Upon uploading a video, the Next.js application initiates an API call to the Strapi server. A loading indicator visually represents the ongoing process.
4. Once the engagement classification report is generated, the interface dynamically presents both the uploaded video and the associated engagement classification, providing a comprehensive overview of the uploaded content.

Step 4: Integration Flow and User Interaction

1. Lecturers access the Next.js application and securely log in.
2. Within the application, a designated section facilitates the hassle-free upload of classroom videos.
3. Lecturers select the desired video file
4. By triggering the "Upload" command, the Next.js application seamlessly transmits the video file and its details to the Strapi backend through an API call.

5. Strapi, upon receiving the data, promptly activates a webhook or server function, which establishes communication with the ML model's API endpoint. The uploaded video is then sent for engagement classification.
6. After processing, the ML model's classification report is communicated back to Strapi, which dutifully stores both the video details and the engagement report within its database.
7. A subsequent API call from the Next.js application to Strapi retrieves the engagement report, categorizing engagement as low, medium, or high.
8. The resulting engagement report is visually presented on the user interface, providing lecturers with valuable insights into the uploaded classroom video's engagement levels.

The pictures of the processes are shown below:

Fig 4.14 Interface of the Strapi Dashboard

Fig 4.15 A new user (admin) is created

Fig 4.16 The Engagement report dashboard

4.6 Tools Used

The following are the tools used in building the frontend and backend of this project:

1. Figma

Figma is a design and prototyping tool used to create user interface (UI) designs and interactive prototypes for web and mobile applications. It is used in frontend development phase to design the visual layout, user interface components, and overall look-and-feel of the application.

2.HTML

Hypertext Markup Language (HTML) is a markup language used to structure content on web pages. It forms the foundation of the frontend, defining the structure and content of the web pages.

3.CSS

Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) is a stylesheet language used to define the presentation and styling of HTML elements; it determines how the HTML elements are displayed, including aspects like colors, fonts, spacing, layout, and responsiveness.

4.Django

It is a high-level Python web framework that simplifies backend development by providing tools for handling databases, URL routing, authentication, and more.

5. Javascript

It is used to add interactivity, behavior, and dynamic content to web pages. It enables the creation of interactive elements, animations, form validations, and real-time updates on the user interface.

6. Strapi

Strapi is an open-source headless content management system (CMS) that empowers developers to efficiently create and manage diverse content for websites and applications. It offers a user-friendly interface for designing custom content structures, which can range from articles to products. Strapi operates as a headless CMS, decoupling content management from presentation, thus allowing content to be seamlessly delivered across various platforms through RESTful or GraphQL APIs. With features like user management, plugin support, and multi-channel content creation, Strapi caters to flexible and tailored content needs, making it an ideal choice for projects requiring dynamic, customizable, and scalable content management.

4.7 System Evaluation

The system was evaluated using alpha testing. The choice of this form of evaluation is the fact that the system has not been deployed for end users to use. It is just available on the localhost computer for the developer to test and evaluate.

4.7.1 Alpha Testing

In this evaluation method, the system was tested internally by the developer using various parameters. The aim is to identify issues with the model's performances, accuracy, and overall functionality before moving on to external testing.

4.7.2. Objectives of Alpha Testing

1. to identify potential bias in the model's predictions
2. to measure the accuracy and precision in the model's predictions

4.7.3 Parameters used in Evaluation

The following are the parameters used to evaluate the performance of the webapp:

1. Accuracy and Precision: This is used to measure how accurately the system detected engagement levels in the video.
2. User Interface and Experience: This is used to measure how user friendly the interface is to upload video and view result.
3. Response Time: This is used to measure how quickly the system processes and analyses the uploaded videos.
4. Compatibility: This is used to measure how well the system works across different browsers.
5. Reliability Across Settings: This is used to test the system's performance in various classroom settings, lightning condition, and video quality.

The system was evaluated using a measurement scale of Excellent, Good, and Bad. The table (*table 4.1*) shows the result of the evaluation after testing of each video.

Table 4.1: Result of Evaluation

Video	Length of Video	Accuracy	Ease of Use	Response Time	Reliability	Compatibility
Video_1	00:25	56%	Good	21sec	Good	Not compatible with Safari browser Compatible with Chrome

						Compatible with Edge
Video_2	00:14	65%	Good	10sec	good	Not compatible with Safari browser Compatible with Chrome Compatible with Edge
Video_3	00:46	45%	Good	32sec	bad	Not compatible with Safari browser Compatible with Chrome Compatible with Edge
Video_4	00:16	60%	Good	15sec	good	Not compatible with Safari browser Compatible with Chrome Compatible with Edge

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to provide a retrospect of the work done, the challenges encountered and as well as the recommendations on improving this project for further study. Finally, this chapter gives a conclusion of the entire design as well as implementation effort which the project attempted to achieve.

5.2 Summary and Conclusion

In this thesis, we present DAiSEE because of the novelty it comes with by having different affective states such as boredom, frustration, confusion, and engagement. The choice of the dataset for this thesis is because it captures the nature of students learning in an environment with varying poses and positions.

Although the state-of-the art model was used to train the dataset which we expected a higher precision due to that, but, the precision achieved was far less than the previous work upon which this thesis was based. The observation we could make is due to the few extracted frames used to build the model.

We also made attempt on giving the model an interface where lecturers can interact with to get the engagement analysis of the students. This could be considered an edge over the existing engagement system and if proper research is further done, the system can be scaled up for real-time implementation.

In conclusion, emotions impact learning and subsequently impacts engagement and attention and if research is properly done in solving the challenges and limitations, student's affective

states will be better understood, lecturers will be able to dynamically change the direction of lectures and learning would not be emotionally exhaustive for both the learner and the tutor.

5.3 Challenges Encountered

During the course of implementing the system, at the frame extraction stage, due to low computation power of the machine used, it took more than 72 hours to extract frames from the videos. We also faced challenges in getting the individual frame-wise engagement of the student while analyzing the video.

Establishing a ground-truth label for the affective states with respect to the position of the camera was also an issue. Questions like should engagement be detected with the students facing the camera or the lecturer? The conflict of choosing the reference point between the camera and the teacher is an avenue for further work.

The inability of the system to recognize faces on glasses was another challenge encountered as it proved that the model had a loophole that needed to be filled upon further research.

5.4 Recommendations

There are still many challenges and problems to solve in order to ensure high-precision emotion detection in engagement systems. Improving the accuracy of the model while decreasing computational load is worth giving attention to. This could be seen in improving the robustness of the dataset to accommodate students from different ages, culture, skin color and gender.

The system could be further improved on to enable real-time detection of engagement with the inclusion of an alert system when the students fall below an engagement threshold.

REFERENCES

1. Aguilar, J., Sánchez, M., Cordero, J., Valdiviezo-Díaz, P., Barba-Guamán, L., & Chamba-Eras, L. (2018). Learning analytics tasks as services in smart classrooms. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 17, 693-709.
2. Aist, G., B. Kort, R. Reilly, R.W. Picard, and J. Mostow. 2002. Experimentally augmenting an intelligent tutoring system with human supplied capabilities: Adding human-provided emotional scaffolding to an automated reading tutor that listens. In: *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS2002)*, Biarritz, France and San Sebastian, Spain, June 2–7, 2002
3. Alkabbany, A. Ali, A. Farag, I. Bennett, M. Ghanoum and A. Farag, “Measuring Student Engagement Level Using Facial Information”, 2019. *IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*, Taipei, Taiwan, 2019, pp. 3337-3341, doi:10.1109/ICIP.2019.8803590
4. Andallaza, T.C.S., Rodrigo, M.M.T., Lagud, M.C.V., Jimenez, R.J.M., Sugay, J.O. (2012). Modeling the affective states of students using an intelligent tutoring system for algebra. In *Proc. International Workshop on Empathic Computing (IWEC)*.
5. Ashwin T.S., Ram Mohana Reddy Guddeti, Affective database for e-learning and classroom environments using Indian students’ faces, hand gestures and body postures, *Future Generation Computer Systems*, Volume 108, 2020, Pages 334-348, ISSN 0167-739X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2020.02.075>.
6. Barrett LF, Adolphs R, Marsella S, Martinez AM, Pollak SD. Emotional Expressions Reconsidered: Challenges to Inferring Emotion From Human Facial Movements. *Psychol Sci Public Interest*. 2019 Jul;20(1):1-68. doi: 10.1177/1529100619832930. Erratum in:

Psychol Sci Public Interest. 2019 Dec;20(3):165-166. PMID: 31313636; PMCID: PMC6640856.

7. Behera, A., Matthew, P., Keidel, A. et al. Associating Facial Expressions and Upper Body Gestures with Learning Tasks for Enhancing Intelligent Tutoring Systems. *Int J Artif Intell Educ* 30, 236-270 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40593-020-00195-2>

8. Bradbury, N. A. (2016). Attention span during lectures: 8 seconds, 10 minutes, or more?. *Advances in Physiology Education*, 40(4), 509–513

9. Calvo RA, D'Mello S. Affect detection: An interdisciplinary review of models, methods, and their applications. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing*. 2010;1: 18–37

10. Canedo, Daniel & Trifan, Alina & Neves, António. (2018). Monitoring Students' Attention in a Classroom Through Computer Vision. 10.1007/978-3-319-94779-2_32.

11. Chen, S., Dai, J., & Yan, Y. (2019). Classroom teaching feedback system based on emotion detection. In 9th International Conference on Education and Social Science (ICESS 2019) (pp. 940-946).

12. Craig, S.D., Graesser, A. C., Sullins, J., & Gholson, B. (2004). Affect and learning: An exploratory look into the role of affect in learning. *Journal of Educational Media*, 29, 241-250.

13. Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1990). *Flow: The psychology of optimal experience*. New York: HarperCollins Publishers, Inc.

14. D'Mello , S. K. , S. D. Craig , B. Gholson , S. Franklin , R. Picard , and A. C. Graesser . 2005 . Integrating affect sensors in an intelligent tutoring system. *Affective*

interactions: The computer . In: The Affective Loop Workshop at the 2005 International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces . New York : AMC Press

15. De Villiers, Bridget & Werner, Amanda. (2018). The relationship between student engagement and academic success. *Journal for New Generation Sciences*. 14. 36.
16. D’Mello, S.K., Craig, S.D., Witherspoon, A., Mcdaniel, B., & Graesser, A. (2010). Automatic detection of learner’s affect from conversational cues. *User Modeling and User-Adapted Interaction*, 18 (1-2), 45-80
17. D’Mello, S., Craig, S.D., Gholson, B., Franklin, S., Picard, R., Graesser, A. (2005). Integrating affect sensors in an intelligent tutoring system. In *Affective Interactions: The Computer in the Affective Loop Workshop* (pp. 7–13).
18. Ekman, P., Friesen, W.V., 1969. The repertoire of nonverbal behavior: Categories, origins, usage, and coding, *Semiotica*, 1: 49-98
19. Ekman, P. (1992). An argument for basic emotions. *Cognition and Emotion*, 6(3), 169–200.
20. Fredricks, J.A., Blumenfeld, P.C., Paris, A.H. (2004). School engagement: Potential of the concept, state of the evidence. *Review of Educational Research*, 74 (1), 59–109, <http://doi.org/10.3102/00346543074001059>.
21. Friedman, I. A. (2006). Classroom management and teacher stress and burnout. In C. M. Evertson & C. S. Weinstein (Eds.), *Handbook of classroom management: Research, practice, and contemporary issues* (pp. 925– 944). Erlbaum.
22. Furrer, C. J., Skinner, E. A., & Pitzer, J. R. (2014). The influence of teacher and peer relationships on students’ classroom engagement and everyday motivational resilience. *Teachers College Record*, 116(13), 101-123.

23. Gelder, B.D. (2006). Towards the neurobiology of emotional body language. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 7(3), 242–249.
24. Gordon, G., Spaulding, S., Westlund, J.K., Lee, J.J., Plummer, L., Martinez, M., Das, M., Breazeal, C. (2016). Affective personalization of a social robot tutor for children's second language skills. In *Proc. of the Thirtieth AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence* (pp. 3951–3957)
25. Graesser, A.C., & Olde, B.A. (2003). How does one know whether a person understands a device? The quality of the questions the person asks when the device breaks down. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 95(3), 524-536.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.95.3.524>
26. Graesser, A. C., & D'Mello, S. (2012). Emotions during the learning of difficult material. In *Psychology of learning and motivation* (Vol. 57, pp. 183-225). Academic Press.
27. Harley, J.M. (2016). Measuring emotions: A survey of cutting-edge methodologies used in computer-based learning environment research. In S. Tettegah & M. Gartmeier (Eds.), *Emotions, technology, design, and learning* (pp.89-119). London: Academic Press.
28. Jayasree, R. (2014). Effective communication. Retrieved from <http://www.laurieford.com>
29. Kaliouby, R., & Robinson, P. (2005). Real-time inference of complex mental states from facial expressions and head gestures. In *Proc. Real-Time Vision for HCI* (pp. 181–200).

30. Kapoor, A., Burleson, W., Picard, R.W. (2007). Automatic prediction of frustration. *International Journal of Human-computer Studies*, 65(8), 724–736.
31. Kim, Y., Soyata, T., & Behnagh, R, F. (2018). Towards emotionally aware AI Smart Classroom: Current Issues and Directions for Engineering and Education. *IEEE Access*, 6, 5308-5331. <http://doi.org/10.1109/access.2018.2791861>
32. Klein, R., and Celik T. (2017). The Wits Intelligent Teaching System: Detecting student engagement during lectures using Convolutional Neural Network. *IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (icip)* (pp. 2856-2860). <http://doi.org/10.1109/ICIP.2017.8296804>
33. Kret, M. E., Stekelenburg, J. J., Roelofs, K., & De Gelder, B. (2013). Perception of face and body expressions using electromyography, pupillometry and gaze measures. *Frontiers in psychology*, 4, 28.
34. Krithika, L. B., & GG, L. P. (2016). Student emotion recognition system (SERS) for e-learning improvement based on learner concentration metric. *Procedia Computer Science*, 85, 767-776.
35. L. Chen, P. Chen and Z. Lin, "Artificial Intelligence in Education: A Review," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 75264-75278, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2988510.
36. Li, Y., Li, F., Chen, J., and Li, H. (2012). An ERP study on the understanding of the distinction between real and apparent emotions. *Neurosci. Lett.* 529, 33–38. doi: 10.1016/j.neulet.2012.08.063
37. Mahmoud, M., & Robinson, P. (2011). Interpreting hand-over-face gestures. In *Proc. International Conference on Affective Computing and Intelligent Interaction* (pp. 248–255).

38. Mrabet, H. E., & Moussa, A. A. (2017). Smart classroom environment via IoT in basic and secondary education. *Transactions on Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence*, 5(4).
39. Oster, H., & Ekman, P. (1978). Facial behavior in child development. In W. A. Collins (Ed.), *Minnesota Symposia on Child Psychology* (Vol. 11, pp. 231-276). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
40. P. Ekman and W. V. Friesen, "Facial Action Coding System: A technique for the measurement of facial movement, Consulting Psychologists Press," Palo Alto, CA, 1978.
41. Pabba, C., & Kumar, P. (2022). An intelligent system for monitoring students' engagement in large classroom teaching through facial expression recognition. *Expert Systems*, 39(1), e12839.
42. Pease, A., & Pease, B. (2006). *The definitive book of body language: How to read others' attitudes by their gestures*. Orion, London, England.
43. Picard RW, Klein J. Computers that recognise and respond to user emotion: Theoretical and practical implications. *Interacting with computers*. 2002;14: 141–169.
44. Prabin Sharma, Shubham Joshi, Subash Gautam, Sneha Maharjan, Vitor Filipe, Manuel Cabral Reis. (2018). *Student Engagement Detection Using Emotion Analysis, Eye Tracking and Head Movement with Machine Learning*.
45. R. Zheng, F. Jiang and R. Shen, "Intelligent Student Behavior Analysis System for Real Classrooms," *ICASSP 2020 - 2020 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, Barcelona, Spain, 2020, pp. 9244-9248, doi: 10.1109/ICASSP40776.2020.9053457.

46. Raca, M., Dillenbourg, P.: System for assessing classroom attention. In: Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Learning Analytics and Knowledge. ACM (2013)
47. Rautaray, S.S., & Agrawal, A. (2015). Vision-based hand gesture recognition for human computer interaction: a survey. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 43(1), 1–54.
48. S. Peng and K. Nagao, "Recognition of Students' Mental States in Discussion Based on Multimodal Data and its Application to Educational Support," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 18235-18250, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3054176.
49. Shuck, B., Albornoz, C., Winberg, M. (2007). Emotions and their effect on adult learning: a constructivist perspective. In Nielsen, S.M., & Plakhotnik, M.S. (Eds.) *Proc. Sixth Annual College of Education Research Conference: Urban and International Education Section* (pp. 108–113).
50. Skinner, E. A., and Pitzer, J. R. (2013). "Developmental dynamics of student engagement, coping, and everyday resilience," in *Handbook of research on student engagement*, eds S. L. Christenson, A. L. Reschly, and C. Wylie (New York, NY: Springer), 21–44. doi: 10.1007/978-1-4614-2018-7_2
51. Soloviev (2018). Machine learning approach for student engagement automatic recognition from facial expressions. *Scientific Publications of the state university of Novi Pazar Series A: Applied Mathematics informatics and mechanics*
52. T. S. Ashwin and R. M. R. Guddeti, "Unobtrusive Behavioral Analysis of Students in Classroom Environment Using Non-Verbal Cues," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 150693-150709, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2947519.

53. Taylor, John & Fragopanagos, Nickolaos. (2005). The interaction of attention and emotion. *Neural networks**: the official journal of the International Neural Network Society. 18. 353-69. 10.1016/j.neunet.2005.03.005.
54. Tulis, Maria & Fulmer, Sara. (2013). Students' motivational and emotional experiences and their relationship to persistence during academic challenge in mathematics and reading. *Learning and Individual Differences*. 27. 35-47. 10.1016/j.lindif.2013.06.003.
55. Turner, J.C., Thorpe, P.K., & Meyer, D.K. (2002). Students' reports of motivation and negative affect: A theoretical and empirical analysis. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 90 (4), 758.
56. Valdiviezo, P., Cordero, J., Aguilar, J., Sánchez, M.: Conceptual design of a smart classroom base on multiagent system. In: de International Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ICAI' 15), pp. 471–477 (2015)
57. Vanneste P, Oramas J, Verelst T, Tuytelaars T, Raes A, Depaepe F, Van den Noortgate W. Computer Vision and Human Behaviour, Emotion and Cognition Detection: A Use Case on Student Engagement. *Mathematics*. 2021; 9(3):287. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math9030287>
58. Vanneste, P., Oramas, J., Verelst, T., Tuytelaars, T., Raes, A., Depaepe, F., & Van den Noortgate, W. (2021). Computer Vision and Human Behavior, Emotion and Cognition Detection: A Use case on Student Engagement. *Mathematics*, 9(3), 287. <http://doi.org/10.3390/math9030287>

59. Whitehill, J., Serpell, Z., Lin, Y.C., Foster, A., Movellan, J.R. (2014). The faces of engagement: Automatic recognition of student engagement from facial expressions. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing*, 5(1), 86–98.
60. Woolf, B. P. (2010). *Building intelligent interactive tutors: Student-centered strategies for revolutionizing e-learning*. Morgan Kaufmann.
61. Zaletelj, J., Košir, A. Predicting students' attention in the classroom from Kinect facial and body features. *J Image Video Proc.* 2017, 80 (2017).
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13640-017-0228-8>
62. Zeng Z, Pantic M, Roisman GI, Huang TS. A survey of affect recognition methods: Audio, visual, and spontaneous expressions. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*. 2009;31: 39–58. 10.1109/TPAMI.2008.52
63. Zhang, X., & Chen, L. (2021). College English smart classroom teaching model based on artificial intelligence technology in mobile information systems. *Mobile Information Systems*, 2021, 1-12.
64. Zhenzhen Luo, Chen Jingying, Wang Guangshuai & Liao Mengyi (2022) A three-dimensional model of student interest during learning using multimodal fusion with natural sensing technology, *Interactive Learning Environments*, 30:6, 1117 1130, DOI: 10.1080/10494820.2019.1710852.

APPENDIX A

```

****

*****

* *

* Project: Student-Engagement Detection *

* *

* Program name: app.py *

* *

*****

****

****

*****

* *

* EMOTION DETECTION SECTION *

* *

*****

****

# import module

# ===== TWO MODEL APPROACH =====
# using face detection and attention detection

import time

from threading import Thread

from flask_cors import CORS
```

```

from flask import Flask, request, Response, jsonify
import traceback
import ultralytics
import numpy as np
from time import sleep
from os.path import exists
from typing import Tuple, Union
import math
import cv2
import os
import numpy as np
import mediapipe as mp
from mediapipe.tasks import python
from mediapipe.tasks.python import vision
MARGIN = 10 # pixels
ROW_SIZE = 10 # pixels
FONT_SIZE = 1
FONT_THICKNESS = 1

TEXT_COLOR = (255, 0, 0) # red
# Create an FaceDetector object.
dir = os.getcwd()

ultralytics.checks()
# load models
attention_model = ultralytics.YOLO(dir + '/models/best.pt')
# face_detector
base_options = python.BaseOptions(
model_asset_path=f"{dir}/models/detector.tflite")

```

```
options = vision.FaceDetectorOptions(base_options=base_options)
detector = vision.FaceDetector.create_from_options(options)
```

```
def _normalized_to_pixel_coordinates(
    normalized_x: float, normalized_y: float, image_width: int,
    image_height: int) -> Union[None, Tuple[int, int]]:
```

```
    """Converts normalized value pair to pixel coordinates."""
```

```
    # Checks if the float value is between 0 and 1.
```

```
    def is_valid_normalized_value(value: float) -> bool:
        return (value > 0 or math.isclose(0, value)) and (value < 1 or
            math.isclose(1, value))
```

```
    if not (is_valid_normalized_value(normalized_x) and
            is_valid_normalized_value(normalized_y)):
```

```
        # TODO: Draw coordinates even if it's outside of the image bounds.
```

```
        return None
```

```
    x_px = min(math.floor(normalized_x * image_width), image_width - 1)
```

```
    y_px = min(math.floor(normalized_y * image_height), image_height - 1)
```

```
    return x_px, y_px
```

```
def apply_attention_detection_model(img):
```

```
    global attention_model
```

```
    predictions = attention_model.predict(img)
```

```
    attentive_count = 0
```

```
    drowsy_count = 0
```

```
    result_str = ""
```

```
    for prediction in predictions:
```

```
        labels = prediction.names
```

```

classes_detected = np.array(prediction.bboxes.cls.cpu(), dtype=np.int32)
print(prediction.bboxes.data, 'attention detected',
classes_detected, labels)
for cls in classes_detected:
if (cls == 0):
attentive_count += 1
else:
drowsy_count += 1
if (len(classes_detected) >= 1):
result_str = f"{{(attentive_count / len(classes_detected)) * 100}}% attentive: {{(drowsy_count /
len(classes_detected)) * 100}}% drowsy"

return result_str, attentive_count, drowsy_count

```

```

def visualize(
image,
detection_result
) -> np.ndarray:
"""Draws bounding boxes and keypoints on the input image and return it.
Args:
image: The input RGB image.
detection_result: The list of all "Detection" entities to be visualize.
Returns:
Image with bounding boxes.
"""
global attention_model
annotated_image = image.copy()
height, width, _ = image.shape
attentive_count_all = 0

```

```

drowsy_count_all = 0

for detection in detection_result.detections:
    # Draw bounding_box
    bbox = detection.bounding_box
    start_point = bbox.origin_x, bbox.origin_y
    end_point = bbox.origin_x + bbox.width, bbox.origin_y + bbox.height
    cv2.rectangle(annotated_image, start_point, end_point, TEXT_COLOR, 3)
    box_region = annotated_image[start_point[1]:end_point[1], start_point[0]:end_point[0]]
    # TODO: comment cv2 image show function
    # cv2.imshow('detected', box_region)
    # pass box_region to your attention detection model
    result_string, attentive_count, drowsy_count = apply_attention_detection_model(
        box_region)
    attentive_count_all += attentive_count
    drowsy_count_all += drowsy_count
    # Draw keypoints
    for keypoint in detection.keypoints:
        keypoint_px = _normalized_to_pixel_coordinates(keypoint.x, keypoint.y,
            width, height)
        color, thickness, radius = (0, 255, 0), 2, 2
        cv2.circle(annotated_image, keypoint_px, thickness, color, radius)

    # Draw label and score
    category = detection.categories[0]
    category_name = category.category_name
    category_name = " if category_name is None else category_name
    probability = round(category.score, 2)
    result_text = category_name + ' (' + str(probability) + ')'

```

```

text_location = (MARGIN + bbox.origin_x,
MARGIN + ROW_SIZE + bbox.origin_y)
cv2.putText(annotated_image, result_text, text_location, cv2.FONT_HERSHEY_PLAIN,
FONT_SIZE, TEXT_COLOR, FONT_THICKNESS)

return annotated_image, attentive_count_all, drowsy_count_all

# to test uploaded data

def apply_face_detection_inference(image):
global detector

mp_image = mp.Image(image_format=mp.ImageFormat.SRGB, data=image)

# Detect faces in the input image.
detection_result = detector.detect(mp_image)

print(detection_result)

# Process the detection result. In this case, visualize it.
image_copy = np.copy(mp_image.numpy_view())

# pass to visualize function that takes in image and detection result and then annotated image
annotated_image, attentive_count_all, drowsy_count_all = visualize(
image_copy, detection_result)

rgb_annotated_image = cv2.cvtColor(annotated_image, cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB)

return rgb_annotated_image, attentive_count_all, drowsy_count_all

def object_detection_module(in_path):
# get video name
name = in_path.split('/')[-1].split('.')[0]

```

```

input_video = cv2.VideoCapture(in_path)
fps = input_video.get(cv2.CAP_PROP_FPS)
frame_width = int(input_video.get(3))
frame_height = int(input_video.get(4))
# output video
output_file_name = name + '-out.mp4'
output_path = os.path.join(
os.getcwd(), 'public', 'videos', output_file_name)
print(output_path, fps, frame_width, frame_height)
fourcc = cv2.VideoWriter_fourcc(*'H264')
video_out = cv2.VideoWriter(
output_path, fourcc, fps, (frame_width, frame_height))
# read video frames
a_count_all = 0
d_count_all = 0
while True:
flag, frame = input_video.read()
if flag:
# The frame is ready and already captured
frame_rgb = cv2.cvtColor(frame, cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB)
frame_out, a_count, d_count = apply_face_detection_inference(
frame_rgb)
a_count_all += a_count
d_count_all += d_count
# cv2.imshow('Video', frame_out)
video_out.write(frame_out)
key = cv2.waitKey(1)
if key == 27:
break

```

```

else:
break

input_video.release()
video_out.release()

return output_file_name, a_count_all, d_count_all

"""
*****

* *

* SERVER CODE SECTION *

* *

*****

"""

app = Flask(__name__)

CORS(app, resources={r"/*": {"origins": "*"}})

UPLOAD_FOLDER = os.path.join(os.path.dirname(__file__), 'public/videos')
ALLOWED_EXTENSIONS = {'mp4'}

app.config['UPLOAD_FOLDER'] = UPLOAD_FOLDER

def allowed_file(filename):
return '.' in filename and filename.rsplit('.', 1)[1].lower() in ALLOWED_EXTENSIONS

@app.route('/', methods=['POST'])
def create_video():
try:

```

```
if 'video' not in request.files:
```

```
    return jsonify({  
        'status': "error",  
        'message': 'No video'  
    }), 400
```

```
video = request.files['video']
```

```
if video.filename == "":
```

```
    return jsonify({  
        'status': "error",  
        'message': 'No selected video'  
    }), 400
```

```
if video and allowed_file(video.filename):
```

```
    timestamp = str(int(time.time()))  
    filename = timestamp + '_' + video.filename
```

```
    filepath = os.path.join(app.config['UPLOAD_FOLDER'], filename)
```

```
    print(filepath, 'filepath')
```

```
    with open(filepath, 'wb') as f:
```

```
        f.write(video.read())
```

```
    output_filename, attentive_count, drowsy_count = object_detection_module(  
        filepath)
```

```
    print(output_filename, attentive_count, drowsy_count)
```

```
    return jsonify({  
        'status': "success",
```

```

'data': {
  'result': output_filename,
  'sum_inference': 1000,
  'engaged_percent': 1000,
  'boredom_percent': 80,
  'confusion_percent': 90,
  'frustration_percent': 110,
  'distracted_percent': 600,
  'attentive_count': attentive_count,
  'drowsy_count': drowsy_count,
  'total_count': attentive_count + drowsy_count
},
'message': 'Video uploaded successfully'
}), 201
else:
return jsonify({
  'status': "error",
  'message': 'You can only upload a video in mp4 format'
}), 500
except Exception as e:
  traceback.print_exc()
  print(e)
return jsonify({
  'status': "error",
  'message': 'Unable to upload video'
}), 500

@app.route('/stream/<filename>', methods=['GET'])
def download_video(filename):

```

```

try:
    filepath = os.path.join(app.config['UPLOAD_FOLDER'], filename)
    print(filepath)
    if os.path.exists(filepath):
        def generate():
            with open(filepath, 'rb') as f:
                while True:
                    # adjust the chunk size as needed
                    chunk = f.read(1024)
                    if not chunk:
                        break
                    yield chunk

        return Response(generate(), mimetype='video/mp4')
    else:
        return jsonify({
            'status': 0,
            'message': 'File not found'
        }), 404
    except Exception as e:
        print(e)
        return jsonify({
            'status': 0,
            'message': 'Error while streaming file'
        }), 500

if __name__ == '__main__':
    app.run(debug=True, port=8000)

```